

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities

WP 2 - Contractual and financial aspects of cross-service integration

D2.1 Legal and financial framework for cross-service integration

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Abstract:	Deliverable 2.1 is aimed to evaluate the framework for delivery of the proposed concept of integrated energy services in practice. The report sounds out the European regulatory framework as well as national regulations affecting NEON. Starting from an analysis of the functioning of the electricity markets in EU, the deliverable proceeds with self-consumption, demand-response, and energy efficiency in buildings. Finally, an evaluation of actual and potential financing schemes as well as financial and technical barriers for NEON is carried out.
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Executive summary

Deliverable 2.1 is the first deliverable of **WP2 Contractual and financial aspects of cross-service integration** and a result of Task 2.1 **Legal and financial conditions for integrated energy service delivery**. It is aimed to evaluate the framework for delivery of the proposed concept of integrated energy services in practice.

The report sounds out the **European regulatory framework** (e.g., the EU Green Deal, the Clean Energy for all Europeans Package, Electricity Market Directives, Renewable Energy Source Directive, Building Efficiency Directive) as well as **national regulations affecting NEON**, splitting the analysis for pilot countries (France, Italy, Spain). Starting from an analysis of the **functioning of the electricity markets in Europe**, the deliverable proceeds with **specific focuses on self-consumption, demand-response, and energy efficiency in buildings**. The analysis is enriched by attention to actual and potential **financing schemes** for the proposed concept of integrated energy services. Finally, an evaluation of actual and potential **financial and technical barriers for NEON** is carried out.

The results of the report will be used as input for the following WP2 tasks, as well as WP4, W5 and WP6 tasks and will help in focusing the service offer and setting the foundation of contractual and business models to be elaborated further in the project. In addition, results will be reflected in the specification of legal and financial requirements for the deployment of the proposed service concepts.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ANESE	National Association of Energy Services Companies
APE	Attestato di Prestazione Energetica / Energy performance certificate
ARERA	Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente / Italian Authority for electricity and natural gas
AS	Ancillary Services
CCL	Certified Capacity Level
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
CEP	Clear Energy Package
CGs	Capacity Guarantees
CNMC	Comisión Nacional de los Mercados y la Competencia / National Markets and Competition Commission
CPI	Consumer Price Index
CRE	Commission de Régulation de l'Énergie / Energy Regulation Commission
CTE	Código Técnico de la Edificación / Technical Building Code
DAFI	Directive Alternative Fuel Initiative
DEEP	De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DR	Demand-Response
DRA	Demand Response Aggregator
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EC	European Commission
EDF	Électricité de France / French Electricity
EEB	Energy Efficient Buildings
EEEF	European Energy Efficiency Fund

EEM	Energy Efficient Mortgage
EEMI	Energy Efficient Mortgages Initiative
EEO	Energy Efficiency Obligations
EIB	European Investment Bank
EPBD	Energy Performance in Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
ESCo	Energy Service Company
ETS	Emission Trading Schemes
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicles
GEFF	Green Economy Financing Facility
GHG	GreenHouse Gas (emission)
GME	Gestore Mercato Energetico / Italian energy market manager
GSE	Gestore Servizi Energetici / Italian energy services manager
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IDAE	Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía / Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving
ISO	Independent System Operator
LNG	Liquefied Natural Gas
LOE	Ley de Ordenación de la Edificación / Building Management Law
LSE	Ley Sector Eléctrico / Electricity Sector Law in Spanish
MB	Mercato del Bilanciamento / Balancing Market
MCP	Market Clearing Price
MCV	Market Clearing Volumes
MGP	Mercato del Giorno Prima / Day Ahead Market
MI	Mercato Intragioraliero / Intraday market
MPEG	Mercato dei prodotti giornalieri / Daily products market

MS	Member States
MSD	Mercato del Servizio di Dispacciamento / Dispatching service market
NBE	Normas Básicas de la Edificación / Basic Building Standards
NEBEF	Block Exchange Notification of Demand Response mechanism
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
OE	Opérateurs d'Effacement
P4P	Pay For Performance
PA	Public Administration
PCE	Piattaforma dei Conti Energia / Energy accounts platform
PCR	Price Coupling of Regions
PEB	Positive Energy Buildings
PF4EE	Private Finance for Energy Efficiency
PNRR	Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza / Italian Recovery and Resilience Plan
PPP	Public Private Partnership
PUN	Prezzo Nazionale Unico / Single National Price
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RITE	Reglamento de instalaciones térmicas en los edificios / Regulation of Thermal Installations in Buildings
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
RTE	Réseau de Transport d'Électricité / Electricity Transmission Network
SIAPÉ	Sistema Informativo sugli Attestati di Prestazione Energetica / Information System on Energy Performance Certificates
SIF	Sustainable Investment Forum (WP leader)
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator

STREPIN	Strategia per la Riqualificazione del Patrimonio Immobiliare Nazionale / Strategy for the Upgrading of National Real Estate
TIDE	Testo Integrato del Dispacciamento Elettrico / Integrated text of electricity dispatching
ToU	Time of Use
TRV	Tarifs Réglementés de Vente / Regulated Sales Tariffs
TSO	Transmission System Operator
VES	Virtual Energy Solutions
VOLL	Value of Lost Load
VPP	Virtual Power Plant

Introduction

NEON project aims at developing and establishing a technical and business ecosystem for integrated energy services for European energy communities. These entities shall be capable of **saving energy, reducing CO₂ emissions, and bringing economic and social benefits** while valorising the energy efficiency and flexibility at demand-side. The project will engage network stakeholders, service providers and final consumers to establish, by a co-creation process, the cross-sectoral arrangements and underlying service concepts.

NEON objectives are aligned with the Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity. This market has been progressively implemented throughout the Union since 1999. The aim is to **deliver practical solutions to contribute to new business opportunities, competitive prices, high standards for services and to the security of supply and sustainability for EU customers** (citizens or businesses).

The Directive (EU) 2019/944 introduced the **Citizen Energy Communities (CECs)** concept as a category of cooperation of citizens or local actors that should be subject to recognition and protection under the European law with the aim to **enable faster market uptake, and facilitate communities, both residential and non-residential, in becoming energy-efficient.** In NEON, the CECs service concepts and business models will be showcased in 4 CEC setups (BERCHIDDA in Italy, DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE in France, POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS in Spain and STAINS CITY in France) serving as early adopters, whereby follow-up replication plans across 7 “follower” communities will be developed during the project.

The analysis carried out in this report at the EU level showed that **Europe is committed to empowering consumers to foster energy transition**, recognized as a key element to reach the environmental and climate goals of the Union. However, for sure **some adjustments are required to fully unlock the energy efficiency and flexibility potential of consumers communities.** The building blocks of the NEON project are widely present in the Clean Energy Package since they are enablers for a sustainable economy. In the end, active consumers are under the spotlight as a crucial subject to drive the transition.

Document objectives and structure

As mentioned above, NEON aims to deliver next-generation integrated energy services for Citizen Energy Communities. For this reason, the **project overall concept was defined to maximise the impact of traditional energy efficiency services**, through holistic optimization of building operation and energy asset utilisation. By doing this, NEON aims to enable integration of:

- **Energy efficiency services** for multi-measure building efficiency improvement (Energy Performance Contracting - EPC/Energy Service Company - ESCo);
- **Optimal energy asset scheduling** (exploiting Renewable Energy Sources - RES, storage and EV charging) for improved self-sufficiency, Virtual Power Plant (VPP)/Virtual Energy Solutions (VES);

- **Demand response services** for grid flexibility improvement;
- **Advanced building control** for optimal operation of heating/cooling systems, lighting, smart appliances, etc.;
- **Use-tailored services** (e.g., scheduling of EV charging or smart appliance control).

This report is targeted to evaluate the legal and financial conditions to implement the proposed concept of integrated energy services listed above. It is expected that it sets the **foundation of contractual and business models** to be further elaborated during the development of the project (e.g., as part of Tasks 2.2 and 4.3). The result of this task will be reflected in the specification of legal and financial requirements for the deployment of the proposed service concepts. The legal aspects of engaging with the consumers under the concept of CECs will be assessed, also towards **identifying potential regulatory barriers** in NEON CECs countries and beyond. In parallel, the existing financial framework will be investigated to **evaluate the financial capacity and interest of different stakeholders** to support the service deployment across its life-cycle phases.

EU regulatory framework affecting NEON

Approximately **three-quarters of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are today linked to the energy sector**, which assumes a key role in averting the worst effects of climate change. **Reaching the net-zero target by 2050 is consistent with** the objective of “holding the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to **limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels**” (EU Commission 2015). Furthermore, the agreement reached at the end of COP26 in Glasgow reaffirmed the importance and urgency of continuing to pursue the 1.5°C target. **We need a systemic change in the production, transportation, and consumption of energy.**

Energy efficiency is a key element of the energy strategy of the European Union. Since 2009, the EU has set ambitious energy and climate targets for 2020, namely 20% greenhouse gas emission reduction, 20% in renewable energy and 20% energy efficiency. After the 2015 Paris Climate Agreement, in 2016 the EU Commission presented its proposal of the Clean Energy for All Package (EU Commission, Directorate-General for Energy 2019) formally approved in 2019 and raised its targets regarding GHG emissions; share of RES in the EU’s energy mix. These **targets have been increased again with the EU Green Deal**, presented at the end of 2019 and starting a long path composed of several key policies and measures to be implemented in its framework. In this context, the EU Commission published, at the beginning of 2020, a proposal for a **European Climate Law, aimed to complement the “2030 climate and energy framework”**. The Climate Law was formally adopted in April 2021, **increasing the 2030 GHG emission reduction target to 55% of net emission and setting the objective of transitioning to a climate-neutral economy by 2050.** Furthermore, the EU defined a specific roadmap toward this goal and presented in July 2021 the **“Fit for 55” package, aimed to profoundly change the way we use energy.** The package contains **12 initiatives, including the amendment of the Energy Efficiency Directive and the revision of the Renewable Energy Directive** as well as brand new proposals.

In the following paragraphs, we are going to focus on the relevant legislative acts for the NEON project, considering the most recent developments. **NEON seeks to join multi-measure energy efficiency interventions in building construction or retrofit phase** (e.g. upgrading building energy supply, efficiency and smartness) **and advanced control capabilities in the building operation phase, providing an integrated approach to energy generation, storage and consumption management.** NEON is based on improved utilisation of proximity RES and storage, optimal scheduling of EV charging points, and advanced control of building systems (such as heat pumps, boilers, lighting, smart appliances). The proposed service concepts and business models will be showcased and tested in 4 CEC setups (residential, non-residential and mixed) serving as early adopters, whereby follow-up replication plans across 8 following communities

EU Green Deal

The **European Green Deal**, launched in 2019, represents the **growth strategy** “to transform the EU into a fair and prosperous society, with a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy where there are no net emissions of greenhouse gases in 2050 and where economic growth is decoupled from resource use” (EU Commission 2019). Since 1990, the EU has made important progress on tackling climate change, having started to modernise the economy while reducing emissions. Indeed, between 1990 and 2018, greenhouse gas emissions decreased by 23%, while the economy grew by 61%.

FIG. 1- Decoupling GDP growth and GHG emissions

Source: *The EU’s track record on climate action - The European Green Deal, 2019:* <https://bit.ly/3hVZaTv>

FIG. 2 - The European Green Deal Targets

Source: Communication from the Commission - The European Green Deal, 2019: <https://bit.ly/3pXBxOR>

At present, the **production and use of energy account for more than 75% of the greenhouse gas emissions in the EU**. The decarbonisation of the European energy system is a key element to **cut net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030**, compared to 1990 levels, and **reach carbon neutrality by 2050**.

Looking at clean energy transition, the EU Green Deal identifies three key crucial drivers to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance the quality of life for citizens:

1. ensuring a **secure and affordable EU energy supply**;
2. developing a **fully integrated, interconnected, and digitalised EU energy market**;
3. prioritising **energy efficiency**, improving the **energy performance of our buildings** and developing a power sector based largely on **renewable sources**.

According to the European Commission, **buildings are responsible for approximately 40% of EU energy consumption and 36% of the energy-related greenhouse gas emissions**. Buildings are therefore the single largest energy consumer in Europe. Heating, cooling, and domestic hot water consumption account for 80% of the energy consumption.

According to the aforementioned drivers, the **European Commission lists a set of objectives**. Here we report those that are more directly linked to the NEON project:

- **build interconnected energy systems** and better-integrated grids to support renewable energy sources;
- promote innovative technologies and **modern infrastructure**;
- boost **energy efficiency** and **eco-design** of products;
- **decarbonise the gas sector** and promote **smart integration** across sectors;
- **empower consumers** and help EU countries to tackle energy poverty.

As mentioned before, the EU Commission officially agreed on the new targets through the new European Climate Law, formally adopted in April 2021. With the proposal of the “Fit for 55” Package, in July 2021, the Commission presented the legislative tools to deliver these targets and transform substantially both the European economy and society towards a sustainable future.

For what most interests this project, the **“Fit for 55” Package combines increased use of renewable energy and greater energy efficiency, updating the related Directives**, as it will be analysed more in-depth in the following paragraphs.

The **Renewable Energy Directive** will raise the bar, setting a higher target to produce by 2030 at least 40% energy from renewable sources. Specific targets are proposed regarding transport, heating and cooling, buildings, and industry.

The proposal for recasting the **EU Directive on Energy Efficiency** raises the ambitions regarding the binding annual targets for reducing energy use at both the national (almost doubled) and European levels. The public sector will play a crucial role in driving the renovation wave, creating new green jobs, reducing energy use and its costs, with a 3% refurbishment rate of its buildings each year.

The Eu Green Deal climate targets:
a 55% cut in greenhouse gas emissions compared to 1990 levels
40% for renewable energy sources in the EU’s energy mix, updating the original RES target of at least 32% of the 2030 climate & energy framework
36-39% energy efficiency target, relative to a baseline scenario established in 2007, updating the original energy efficiency target of at least 32.5% of the 2030 climate & energy framework

The REPowerEU Plan, launched on 18 May 2022, updates objectives and strategies in response to the energy market crisis which it is affecting the EU: there is the urgency to end the EU’s dependence on Russian fossil fuels, on one hand, and to tackle the climate crisis on the other.

The plan will be backed by The Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) which will support, coordinate, and finance cross-border and national infrastructure as well as energy projects and

reforms. €225 billion is already available and, in addition, the European Commission proposes to increase the RRF financial envelope with €20 billion in grants from the sale of EU Emission Trading System (ETS) allowances.

REPowerEU is built on three main actions: saving energy, diversification of energy supplies, and accelerating roll-out of renewable energy.

Saving energy

Increasing energy efficiency target from 9% to 13% under the “Fit for 55” package of European Green Deal. The European Commission has published the “EU Save Energy Communication” which describes short-term behavioral changes which could cut gas and oil demand by 5%.

Diversification of energy supplies

Diversifying energy supplies and securing adequate levels of Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) imports and higher pipeline gas deliveries from suppliers. The EU Energy Platform will enable voluntary common purchases of gas, LNG, and hydrogen by pooling demand, optimizing infrastructure, and coordinating outreach to suppliers. Following the good results of the common vaccine purchasing program, the Commission will consider a similar program for gas purchases on behalf of participating Member States.

Accelerating the rollout of renewables

2030 RES target has been increased by 5% (from 40% to 45%) in order to trigger new initiatives, such as: EU Solar Strategy to double solar photovoltaic capacity by 2025 and to install 600GW by 2030; Solar Rooftop Initiative with a phased-in legal obligation to install solar panels on new public, commercial and residential building, setting a target of 10 million tonnes of domestic renewable hydrogen; Biomethane Action Plan to set out a new biomethane industrial partnership and financial incentives.

The Clean Energy for all Europeans Package

In 2016, the EU Commission proposed a **set of eight ambitious legislative acts called “Clean Energy Package for all Europeans” or CEP**. The objective was to rewrite the energy policy framework, addressing the five dimensions of the Energy Union:

- a) energy security;
- b) internal energy market;
- c) energy efficiency;
- d) decarbonisation of the economy;
- e) research, innovation, and competitiveness.

The CEP, formally adopted in 2019, defined the updated targets to 2030, later modified by the EU Green Deal and the following legislative acts. The package settled the right balance among different decision-making levels: European, national and regional level.

The Clean Energy Package **includes four Directives and four Regulations**, that focus on wide topics such as redesign of the electricity market; renewable energy; energy efficiency and energy performance of buildings. Furthermore, the CEP requests the Member States for "National Energy and Climate Plan" (NECP), covering from 2021 to 2030.

Electricity market Directives

Governance of the Energy Union Regulation (EU) 2018/1999

The Regulation faces the **need for transparent and reliable governance and long-term planning**. It sets a new governance system – and therefore common rules for planning, reporting, and monitoring – **to ensure a coherent implementation and coordination of national energy strategies** on the internal energy market, energy security and energy efficiency. At the same time, it aims to guarantee alignment with the ambition cycles under 2030 targets and the Paris Agreement.

The Regulation, starting from the decade 2021-2030, decided to ask each Member State (MS) to develop a **ten-year National Energy and Climate Plans based on a common template**, with the target of 2050 climate goals. The final plans have been submitted at the end of 2019 and will be updated by 30 June 2024 to reflect the EU increased climate ambition. Contextually, **Member States must develop national long-term strategies** and ensure consistency with their national energy and climate plans. The Commission shall publish every year a report on the State of the Energy Union and a two-year Energy Union progress report.

In 2020, the Commission produced – both at the European and national level – an **assessment of NECPs to drive forward the green transition and to promote economic recovery** through integrated energy and climate planning. The assessment showed that the EU was on track to go beyond its 2030 greenhouse gas emissions reduction target of that time of 40% – with a combined impact of roughly 41%. At the same time, the results of the process – among other things – laid the foundations for the revision of the new 2030 Climate Target Plan and later of the Energy Efficiency Directive (EU) 2018/2002.

Directive (EU) 2019/944 and Regulation (EU) 2019/943 on the internal market for electricity

- **Electricity Regulation (EU) 2019/943**

Proposed in the context of the Clean Energy Package, the Regulation was built to define the **principles for the development of a fully integrated internal electricity market** in Europe. The focus of the act is on the wholesale market and network operation.

- **Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944**

As per the coupled Regulation, the Directive was presented in the Clean Energy Package, providing a comprehensive revision of the previous directive 2009/72/EC. It sets the **framework for the generation, transmission, distribution, supply, and storage of electricity**.

Given the new market dynamics, related new climate targets and new possible technical developments, the legislative act was aimed to adapt the regulatory framework with a specific

emphasis on the opportunities offered by the participation of consumers in the market and to cross-border cooperation.

As and more than the Electricity Regulation (EU) 2019/943, the Directive's objective is to build an actual internal energy market, grounded on common rules that can ensure clean and affordable energy for all.

At the same time, the Directive encourages a **new paradigm regarding the role of the consumers, moving to the concept of "active customers" who can self-produce electricity and operate either directly or in an aggregated manner**. The innovation is the possibility of **selling the exceeding in this production**, also through agreements for electricity purchase and the **direct participation in flexibility and energy efficiency mechanisms**. Furthermore, the Directive stresses the possibility for consumers to take advantage of the direct participation in the market through Demand-Response (DR) mechanisms, i.e., modifying their consumption based on market signals and therefore experiencing lower energy prices or other incentives.

The Electricity Directive introduces the notion of "Citizen Energy Community", stated as follows:

Article 2(11) Electricity Directive – "Citizen Energy Community"

A legal entity that:

- a) is based on voluntary and open participation and is effectively controlled by members or shareholders that are natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises;
- b) has for its primary purpose to provide environmental, economic, or social community benefits to its members or shareholders or to the local areas where it operates rather than to generate financial profits; and
- c) may engage in generation, including from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services to its members or shareholders.

Energy services provided by Citizen Energy Communities include **aggregation, generation, consumption, storage, sharing and distribution** – also using the existing network, in agreement with the local Distribution System Operator (DSO) –, **as well as energy-related services**. CECs, like Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) examined more in-depth in the next paragraph, aim to **provide economic, environmental or social benefits** rather than financial profits to members of the community or to the local area where they are established. They are built on **participation (open and voluntary) and engagement** of citizens, small enterprises and local authorities.

Renewable Energy Source (RES) Directive

Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001 - RED II

The Directive on the promotion of the use of renewable energy sources is better known as RED II as it is a full recast of the Directive 2009/28/EC, or RED I. It established a series of **measures to help the EU reach its 32%, and several sub-targets, for renewable energy sources** in the EU's energy mix by 2030. According to the new 55% greenhouse gases reduction target, **a 38-40% RES share in final energy consumption by 2030 will be required**: the EU has now to revise the RED II and related legislation to align this target (EEA 2021). The process is ongoing.

The Figure below shows EU-27 shares of renewable energy sources (including only certified biofuels complying with the RED sustainability criteria), the indicative 2020 target, and the 2030 target.

FIG. 3 - Progress towards renewable energy source targets for EU-27

Source: European Environment Agency (EEA), 2021: <https://bit.ly/3CycgQi>

The current Directive, without setting binding national targets, maintains the existing 2020 target defined by RED I as binding baseline levels (or minimum renewable energy sources levels). Reaching RED II objectives is linked to a **more integrated process of monitoring, reporting, and improving national climate and energy policies** as defined in Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 on Governance of the Energy Union and specifically national energy and climate plans.

RED II legally defines and targets to **support renewable self-consumers and renewable energy communities**. Indeed, **Article 21 states that consumers are entitled to become renewables self-consumers** and, both individually or through aggregators, to produce, store and sell the potential energy surplus. **In Article 22, the RED II introduces the concept of "Renewable Energy Community"**. These RECs are entitled to produce, consume, store, and sell renewable energy, including through renewables power purchase agreements. They are also entitled to share and exchange, within the renewable energy community, renewable energy produced as well as to access all suitable energy markets either directly or through aggregation, in a non-discriminatory way.

Article 2(16) Renewables Directive – "Renewable Energy Community"

A legal entity that:

- a) in accordance with the applicable national law, is based on open and voluntary participation, is autonomous, and is effectively controlled by shareholders or members that are in the proximity of the renewable energy projects that are owned and developed by that legal entity;
- b) the shareholders or members of which are natural persons, SMEs, or local authorities, including municipalities;
- c) the primary purpose of which is to provide environmental, economic, or social community benefits for its shareholders or members or for the local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits.

RECs somehow represent a subset of CECs, as defined in Article 2(11) of the Electricity Directive, **offering generation, distribution** – also using the existing network, in agreement with the local DSO – **consumption, storage, sale, aggregation, supply, sharing of renewable energy** (electrical and thermal), **and energy-related services**.

Energy Performance of Building Directive

Energy Performance in Buildings Directive (EU) 2018/844 and 2021 proposal

Given the relevance of the building sector in terms of energy consumption and GHG emissions¹, policy interventions have always played a crucial role in reaching the climate targets of the European Union.

In 2018, the Energy Performance in Buildings Directive (EU) 2018/844 (or EPBD) amended and updated the Directive 2010/31/EU. The Directive defined **specific energy efficiency targets for**

¹ According to 2020 data, buildings are responsible for about 40% of the energy consumption in Europe, and 36% of greenhouse gas emissions from energy. Nonetheless, every year only 1% of these buildings are involved in energy efficient renovation.

new buildings regarding the **minimum energy performance requirements, energy certification, monitoring and control of energy use** and the new obligations for the installation of **electricity recharging points**.

Moreover, the legislative act contained the **definition of Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)** as well as a specific methodology to calculate it. The indicator is **aimed to assess the flexibility of a building in adapting its operations** according to the needs of both users/inhabitants and of the grid. Furthermore, it was **established to improve energy performance and efficiency of building as well**, considering features for enhanced functionalities or capabilities linked to more interconnected and intelligent devices.

At the end of 2020, the European Commission presented its **Renovation Wave Strategy** (EU Commission 2020) **to improve the energy performance of buildings**, at least **double renovation rates** in the following ten years and make sure renovations lead to **higher energy and resource efficiency**. To achieve the at least 55% emissions reduction target for 2030, the **EU must reduce buildings' greenhouse gas emissions by 60%, their energy consumption by 14%, and the energy consumption of heating and cooling by 18%**. New buildings were already positively affected in terms of energy efficiency by European policy and funding. Today, they consume only half the energy of those built over 20 years ago. Unfortunately, about 85% of the actual building stock in Europe was built more than 20 years ago, and 85-95% of these will still be standing in 2050.

A new revision of the EPBD was therefore essential to the Renovation Wave Strategy. At the end of 2021, in the context of the “Fit for 55” Package, the Commission made its proposal for a recast of the Directive (EU) 2018/844c to follow up on the key elements of the three focus areas² of the strategy, including the **intention to propose mandatory minimum energy performance standards**. The recast sets the vision for achieving a zero-emission and fully decarbonised building stock by 2050 through measures aimed to increase the renovation rate for the buildings in the lower spectrum of energy performance.

Several aspects of energy efficiency were covered, both for private and public actors, on the technical and financial sides. **All the buildings shall be zero-emission by 2040**, with new public buildings that must fulfil the requirement already by 2027. The **worst-performing 15%** of the EU building stock **will have to be refurbished** to shift by 2030 **from Class G to at least Class F** in Energy Performance Certificate. Also, in this case, public and non-residential buildings must comply by 2027. **Residential buildings should be upgraded further to at least Class E by 2033**. Member States can set their standards in addition. In general, all the buildings undergoing major renovations, buildings offered for sale or rent, and all public buildings will be obliged to have an Energy Performance Certificate. Residential and commercial buildings will be required to build charging **infrastructure for electric vehicles as well as to promote parking spots for bicycles**. The disclosure of history and information on buildings will be enhanced through a **“building renovation passport”** to facilitate users in planning a low cost and step-by-step renovation. To ensure comparability at the European level, **National Energy and Climate Plans will integrate National Building Renovation Plans and include by 2040 specific roadmaps for the phase-out**

² Tackling energy poverty and worst-performing buildings; public buildings and social infrastructure showing the way; and decarbonising heating and cooling.

from fossil fuels in heating and cooling. On the financial side, the revised Directive invites the Member States to include renovation topics in public and private financial rules, establishing specific and appropriate instruments, particularly for low-income households. All the financial incentives on fossil fuels for heating and cooling in buildings will have a sunset clause, but the Member States can independently choose to ban their use.

- **Energy Efficiency Directive (EU) 2018/2002 and 2021 proposal**

In 2018, the Directive on Energy Efficiency (2018/2002) amended the Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency, as part of the “Clean Energy for all Europeans” package. The amending directive set an **energy efficiency target for 2030 of at least 32.5% and introduced new rules to extend consumer rights and improve access to smart metering, smart billing, and consumption information.** The baseline for the energy efficiency target is set relative to the 2007 model projections for 2030. The targets defined in the Directive must be achieved collectively across the EU, with each Member State obliged to achieve a minimum amount of end-use energy savings in a specific period: the first one ran from 2014 until 2020, the second period covers 2021 to 2030. This obligation derives from Article 7 of the legislative act.

- After the withdrawal of the UK, the **overall energy consumption should be lower than 1,128 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe)** of primary energy and/or lower than 846 Mtoe of final energy.
- The energy savings obligation in end-use, introduced in the 2012 Directive, was extended too, under the amending directive. Each EU country will have to reach **additional savings of 0.8% each year of final energy consumption** for the 2021-2030 period. Cyprus and Malta will have to achieve 0.24% each year instead.

Given the increase of EU climate ambitions, linked to the new Green Deal, the EU Commission has revised again several EU energy and climate rules and put forward a proposal, in July 2021, for recasting the EU Directive on Energy Efficiency (EU Commission 2021) as part of the package “Delivering on the European Green Deal”.

Under the 2018 Directive, each Member State was required to publish its National Energy and Climate Plans, stating how they intended to achieve their energy efficiency targets. After the submission of all the 27 NECPs in 2020, the Commission assessed their cumulative impact and observed how the 32.5% target was missed, reaching only a 29.4% reduction of final energy consumption and 29.7% for primary energy consumption. The assessment was preparatory to the drafting of the Climate Target Plan in which the EU Commission estimated the **new targets for energy efficiency: the overall energy consumption should be lower than 1,023 Mtoe** of primary energy and **lower than 787 Mtoe of final energy in 2030.** Looking at the 32.5% target on a 2007 consumption projection basis, this choice is **equivalent to new targets of 39% and 36% respectively.** Anyway, in the proposal the Commission based these figures with respect to the updated 2020 baseline scenario, therefore the new targets are expressed as a 9% reduction by 2030.

One of the key drivers for energy efficiency improvements is the obligation for the Member States to achieve specific annual energy savings in end-use consumption. The **proposal seeks to almost double the annual energy savings obligations in end-use,** set at 0.8% per year (except for Cyprus

and Malta), to 1.5% from 2024 to 2030. This proposal seeks to increase the national effort in strategic sectors such as building, transport and industry using Energy Efficiency Obligations (EEO) schemes³ or alternative policy measures.

National regulations affecting NEON (France, Italy, Spain)

Electricity markets in Europe

Production, interchange, and delivery of electricity in each European Member State, as well as the relative monetary flows, rely on both physical and intangible infrastructures. **Markets are entitled to an efficient allocation of energy;** technical controls avoid any possible electricity system collapse. At any time, during the day, **the system must constantly match generation, consumption and energy losses ensuring the equilibrium between demand and supply.** The absence of this balance will deviate grid frequency from its reference value causing a system breakdown. **Distributed Energy Resources (DER)** – i.e., local generation units – are widely present in the system and **may change the grid conditions** not only from day to day but also intraday.

FIG. 4 - Graphs of forecasted, scheduled and actual demand for a typical autumn day, 2022

Source: Esios, System Operator Information System (In spanish: Sistema de Información del Operador del Sistema): <https://bit.ly/3E7IST4>

The electricity market is **divided into four different markets, which intervene in different time frames,** due to the specific technical characteristics of the traded asset, to ensure the stability of the system and to avoid potential failures:

³ Defined in Article 7 of the Directive (EU) 2018/2002: the Member States may identify obligated parties among energy distributors, retail energy sales companies and transport fuel distributors or retailers to achieve the amount of savings required at the national level.

- **forward and futures markets;**

This market consists of contracts to deliver or consume electricity in a certain future at a certain price. It may start several years before the day before the actual exchange of electricity.

FIG. 5 - Graphs for the following day's markets in a day of autumn, 2022

Source: Esios, System Operator Information System (In spanish: Sistema de Información del Operador del Sistema);

<https://bit.ly/3UOXFrs>

- **day-ahead markets;**

On the Day-ahead market, the electricity is traded the day before the actual delivery. These markets are strategic to ensure balance on the grid at the end of the day, based on planned generation and consumption.

FIG. 6 - Graphs for the following day's markets in a day of autumn, 2022

Source: Esios, System Operator Information System (In spanish: Sistema de Información del Operador del Sistema):

<https://bit.ly/3TynriS>

- **intra-day markets;**

The electricity is traded on the intra-day market on the day on which it is delivered. The role of these markets is to correct eventual shifts with respect to the day ahead nomination, due to unexpected events such as a change in weather forecasts.

FIG. 7 - Example chart for the different intraday markets in an autumn day, 2022

Source: Esios,
System Operator
Information System
(In spanish: Sistema
de Información del
Operador del
Sistema):

<https://bit.ly/3hJT6Re>

- **balancing markets.**

Balancing markets are aimed to solve imbalances in real-time. The match between demand and supply is up to the Transmission System Operator (TSO) which has access to Ancillary Services (AS) to maintain grid stability and security. The ancillary services are based on reserves that can be activated in case of emergency when an imbalance occurs.

FIG. 8 - Example of graph of the settings to raise the available energy in an autumn day, 2022

Source: Esios,
System Operator
Information System
(In spanish: Sistema
de Información del
Operador del
Sistema):

A project that is worth to be mentioned is the **Price Coupling of Regions (PCR)⁴**, where European Power Exchanges **try to harmonise the European electricity markets** by developing common assets, a single price coupling algorithm and PCR Matcher and Broker SW, to be used to calculate electricity prices across Europe. The Project is creating a **governance structure based both on a Co-Ownership Agreement and a Co-Operation Agreement** among exchanges. The main benefits of an integrated European electricity market are increased liquidity, transparency, efficiency, and social welfare. At the same time, it guarantees the overall welfare, and optimal use of electricity network constraints. Furthermore, implicit trading removes unnecessary risks of trading cross-border capacity and electricity separately.

PCR aims to couple the following countries: Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom.

⁴ PCR Project - Main features: <https://bit.ly/3KauzgY>

FIG.9 - PCR users and members

Source: PCR Project - Main features: <https://bit.ly/3KauzgY>

PCR users and members

The calculation of the price, as well as the increased transparency of prices and electricity flows and the optimization of the overall welfare, are up to Euphemia, a single price coupling algorithm.

Looking at **retail energy markets**, 2020 data show that there is **room for further improvement**, according to ACER Market Monitoring Report (ACER 2022). **While market concentration rates are still significant on the supply side, demand-side consumers are not playing the role they could** with only a small portion of them engaging the markets. The **enhancement of consumers** may be reached by supporting **price comparison tools** (CEER 2021) as well as helping them in understanding their consumption and market price definition process. Most of all, **smart meters** have to be widely distributed **to increase knowledge and support the further update of dynamic price contracts**, offering benefits to both the final customer and the energy system. At the same time, smart meters might expose consumers to higher wholesale price volatility and require an accurate analysis of the additional risks and drawbacks of these contracts.

Demand response market

Our society continually demands electricity to produce goods in factories, to run businesses and companies, and to power the lives of households and throughout the day there are changes in demand. According to Fouruli et al. (2021), the increasing investments in renewable generation and Distributed Energy Resources, located both at the transmission and the distribution grids, represent one of the main transformations of the power system. Those sources are responsible for **new challenges posed to the operation of both the transmission grid**, where ramping availability needs to be guaranteed by new balancing and frequency services, **and the distribution grid**, where new flexibility services and investments by the Distribution System Operators (DSOs) are required to handle reverse power flows, and new congestion and voltage issues (IRENA 2019). For this reason, **DSOs are seeking products and mechanisms capable of ensuring the required**

flexibility in the market, like adapting generation and/or consumption configurations by responding to external signals.

This mechanism of **adapting electricity demand to its supply, modifying consumption, is known as demand-response** and potentially involves all the consumers, both on the industrial and on the domestic side. For example, enterprises may choose to modify their operational processes as well as households may use their home appliances when the relative electricity price is lower. **DR importance has raised at the domestic level, thanks to the maturation and advances in information technology and control.** DR is already working for large players in the market but **remains relatively new for small and medium prosumers, largely due to the absence of appropriate business models.** According to the Northeast Energy Efficiency Partnerships (2016), we are witnessing a “revolution in customer engagement” (NEEP 2016).

DR schemes have a **key role in increasing the efficiency of the market, integrating new types of demand, increasing competition, empowering consumers and promoting active participation, reducing expensive investment in peak generation, and usually reducing GHG emissions.** The main enablers are represented by **smart meters, home automation and management systems.** DR can occur with the **direct intervention** of the consumer (i.e., shifting consumption in response to price changes) **or automatically**, based on automated systems that adjust the consumption of electricity responding to prices, forecasts and needs.

There exist two mechanisms of demand response: implicit and explicit. Both kinds are **complementary and should coexist** to ensure consumer choices and enable an efficient energy system.

Implicit DR schemes are those where consumers shift their load based on time-varying electricity prices, reflecting different costs of electricity in different timeframes, such as:

- **Time of Use rates:** within specific periods of time electricity price may be lower or higher (e.g., at night);
- **Real-time pricing:** the cost of energy on the wholesale market directly defines prices continuously;
- **Critical peak pricing:** when specific events affect upward the expectations on energy prices, they can be raised artificially by suppliers;
- **Critical time rebates:** instead of artificially rising prices, the supplier may reward consumers for their consumption reduction.

Usually, the effect of this flexibility in consumption is a **reduction in electrical bills, that may be coupled with specific performance-based incentives (P4P)** integrated into the contracts between suppliers and consumers.

Explicit DR schemes are those where **end-users react to specific requests** to adjust their consumption behaviour. It is **usually managed by an aggregator** that can be an independent service provider or a supplier. Consumers indicate in advance the amount of flexibility they can have during the day, offering it on different markets: wholesale, reserves, and balancing. This mechanism, based on direct payments to consumers, is mostly applied to industrial consumers

based on their specific weight on the market. CECs may as well play a similar role, with respect to single independent consumers unable to ensure the same load reduction.

Different kinds of explicit DR schemes are applied to specific energy markets. **Balancing markets** are the ones used to balance energy fluctuations and since explicit DR potentially works in a very short time they are offered very often in this segment. Market coupling in all timeframes, including close to real-time balancing, would generate additional welfare benefits of more than €1.5 billion per year and strongly reduce the need for backup fossil fuel power plants, thus saving significant GHG emissions.

In some cases, e.g. in Italy, an administrative shortage pricing mechanism is already operating for dispatching: when an imbalance occurs, the TSO is required to resort to rolling disconnections of loads either in the scheduling phase of the Ancillary Services Market or, with at least 30 minutes notice, in the real-time phase of this market. In this case, the imbalance settlement price corresponds to the Value of Lost Load (VOLL) (ACER 2021).

Another important market for explicit DR schemes is the **capacity market**, where the **flexibility mechanism can ensure peak shaving** and therefore sufficient capacity on the grid.

In general, **DR flexibility could be used in day-ahead scheduling to optimise production and consumption. Also, it could be used on a real-time basis in case of deviations from the original scheduling.**

NEON proposes a hybrid demand response (DR) model which combines explicit (incentive-based operational interventions) and implicit DR (price based behavioural interventions) mechanisms. This way, NEON will facilitate service providers and aggregators in unlocking the flexibility potential to provide ancillary service to grid stakeholders (e.g., congestion control, peak caving), both at a building and community (aggregated) level.

Among the most widely diffuse approaches, there are the interruptibility ones, involving both industrial and retail consumers. They refer to services provided on different time scales based on national programs, that range from consumption reduction in times of scarcity to automatic DR mechanisms to counter unforeseen needs of the grid.

Interruptibility schemes pose a problem with market fragmentation among different member states: indeed, fragmentation may lead to suboptimal use of the resources. For better integration of this mechanism, **interruptibility schemes should exploit cross-border participation.** Stand-alone interruptibility schemes should be left only when no parallel procurement channels exist, or to start the development of new DR products or services.

FIG. 10 - Interruptibility schemes in Europe – 2020

Source: ACER based on information provided by the NRAs and, in case of France, publicly available information: <https://bit.ly/3hVU7Cu>

Self-consumption

Self-consumption occurs when individuals, condominiums, companies, or local authorities choose to **consume electricity directly produced nearby and associated with them**. An example of production units is **photovoltaic panels or mini wind generators**. Self-consumption gives access to a series of economic and environmental advantages:

- **Savings:** an increase in self-production corresponds to a **reduction of costs of the variable components of the bill** (e.g., network charges and related taxes such as, depending on the national regulation - excise duties and VAT);
- **Income:** producing energy with photovoltaic systems or a mini-wind generator can represent a source of income thanks to the **incentive mechanisms**;
- **Tax benefits** (deductions or super-amortization);
- **Environmental benefits:** since the energy is produced by renewable sources, the **emissions of CO₂ or other greenhouse gases are avoided**.

On a regulatory level, the transposition of the Electricity Directive aimed to create adequate frameworks for demand-side flexibility and the active participation of all energy consumers is still ongoing in most of the EU Member States. Only a few⁵ paved the way in outlining aggregators,

⁵ Germany, Denmark, France, and Hungary

independent aggregators, active consumers, and citizen energy communities as well as the opening of their markets and products for new entrants.

Energy efficiency in buildings

NEON will position the energy efficiency, under the EPC, as one of the core service concepts, and integrate it with the **flexibility potential to be unlocked at the demand side, as part of the P4P**. As a market-based instrument for the implementation of energy efficiency in buildings, EPC is a contractual arrangement between a beneficiary (e.g., building owner or occupants) and a service provider. **Two EPC models will be considered:**

- **“Shared savings”**, with a split of the cost savings for a predetermined time interval, while the risks are taken by both ESCo and consumer;
- **“Guaranteed savings”** model, when the ESCo guarantees a certain level of energy savings, protecting the client from any performance risk.

FRANCE

The analysis of French regulations affecting NEON has to start from a very quick overview of the integrated National Energy and Climate Plan, the key points of which are summarised below. The integrated National Energy and Climate Plan of France builds on the **Multiannual Energy Planning and the National Low-Carbon Strategy**; the guiding objectives were to decarbonise the energy system and to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050. In particular, **France’s 2030 main targets** are:

- **-20% of final energy consumption** compared to 2012;
- **33% of renewable energy** in gross final energy consumption;
- **-37% of GHG emissions** except for land use, land-use change and forestry and except for sectors covered by the European carbon market (EU ETS) compared to 2005

France’s NECP also identifies many specific research and innovation requirements in non-energy-related sectors: process improvements relating to “carbon” and environmental efficiency, optimisation, recycling and reuse of resource, social innovations (changes to behaviours and attitudes, ownership of change, etc.) and organisational innovations (public policies etc.)⁶.

⁶ Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan for France: <https://bit.ly/3hznomi>

Wholesale and retail electricity markets in France

- The wholesale market in France

FIG. 11 - Wholesale electricity market in France

Source: Commission de Régulation de l'Énergie (CRE): <https://bit.ly/36eazLP>

The participants in the wholesale market are:

- producers who trade and sell their production;
- suppliers who trade and supply electricity before selling it to the final client;
- brokers/traders purchasing electricity for resale and thus favouring market liquidity.

The **wholesale market in France is divided into two segments**; the future and the spot one. **The futures market allows players to negotiate bilaterally the delivery of electricity**, from years before to the day ahead of the actual exchange, using standardised financial products to ensure the efficiency of trading. The market aims to allow the hedging of costs and revenues related to electricity production and consumption.

FIG. 12 – Structure of the energy market in France

Source: Image processed by SIF

Regarding the market structure scheme presented at the beginning of this chapter, the **French spot market includes both the day-ahead market and the intraday market**. These are managed by the company **EpexSpot**.

The **day-ahead market operates via blind auctions**, which take place **once a day, every day, during the year**. The order book closes at 12:00 and all the orders regarding each hour of the following day must be submitted before then. The EpexSpot algorithm aggregates orders to establish demand and supply curves, whose intersection defines the Market-Clearing Price (MCP), determined for each delivery period and applied to all buyers and sellers. The executed buy volume equals the overall executed sell volume for each delivery period (Market Clearing Volumes - MCV).

Capacity Market

Capacity market in France was established in 2016 to ensure the security of supply – especially through peak winter period – through the **obligation of obligated parties (called “Acteurs Obligés”)** and by **providing generation and demand response capacities in exchange for remuneration**.

There exist two kinds of actors in this market:

- **Capacity operators**, involved in generation and demand response capacity. The **Certified Capacity Level (CCL) is based on a MW availability commitment** over a year established in a certification contract with Réseau de Transport d'Électricité (RTE). The TSO issues **Capacity Guarantees (CGs)** to contract holders, which are equivalent to

customers' consumption levels in peak hours. These CGs can be sold to obligated parties OTC or at EPEX SPOT market sessions. Public tenders have been replaced by this mechanism, to ensure more capacity to support the grid during peak hours.

- **Obligated parties** are required to demonstrate on an annual basis their ability to meet customer energy demand during peak winter periods. To meet this obligation, they must hold. Obligated parties are **mainly suppliers, as well as end consumers and system operators**.

Fig. 13 - Global demand response mechanisms in France's electricity market

Source: Image processed by SIF

FIG. 14 - Participation in the capacity market

Source: Le Réseau de Transport d'Électricité: <https://bit.ly/3i27lgS>

Peak management assume a crucial role in the **French market that accounts for half of the thermosensitive market in Europe, due to the high penetration of electric heating**: a 1°C drop in temperature increase peak consumption by 2.4 GW on a national level⁷.

To address this issue, **RTE identifies the peak days during the year of delivery**, in the day ahead, as PP1 for obligated parties and PP2 for operators. During these days both actors of the market must fulfil their respective obligations from 7:00 to 15:00 and from 18:00 to 20:00, during the winter period, from October 1st to March 31st.

15 PP1 days (business days excluding holidays) are notified each delivery year, distributed as follows:

- 11 PP1 days are notified over the January-February-March period;
- 4 PP1 days are notified over the November-December period.

The number of PP2 days is between 15 and 25 days per delivery year and are of two types:

- 15 PP1 days which are also PP2 days;
- 0 to 10 days which are PP2 days excluding PP1 days.

● The retail market in France

According to the French Energy Regulatory Commission (Commission de Régulation de l'Énergie - CRE) **retail consumers are those with a yearly consumption below 10 MWh and whose subscribed power is less than 36 kVA**.

Since 1 July 2007, the energy **market was fully opened to competition** and consumers have been free to choose their energy supplier. Retail consumers can choose between two types of offers:

- market products with prices freely set by suppliers;
- regulated sale tariffs (Tarifs Réglementés de Vente - TRV), set by the government and proposed by the incumbent operators (Électricité de France - EDF and the 162 local distribution companies).

Regulated sale tariffs are governed by Articles L.337-4 to L.337-9 and R. 337-18 et seq. of the French Energy Code.

● Self-consumption in France

Before 2016, there was no specific framework for self-consumption in France. It was possible only in the RES support schemes but only regarding the remunerated surplus fed into the grid, that often corresponded to all the energy produced. The **Energy Transition for Green Growth Act (2015)** changed the rules, creating a framework that allowed the development of self-

⁷ For more information: <https://bit.ly/35mDSvF>

consumption, and experienced increased interest. This framework was designed through an ordinance, ratified by the Parliament in February 2017, and the decree n° 676/2017. At last, the framework was strengthened with the law dated 24 February 2017⁸ ratifying the ruling of 27 July 2016, acknowledging, and governing self-consumption.

The Law defines both:

- **individual self-consumption**, where electricity is produced and consumed simultaneously in a specific location by a single person/household being that one the only beneficiary of the installation.
- **collective self-consumption**, where electricity is produced and consumed by several consumers and producers located on the same low-voltage grid, in those type of self-consumption installations is not necessary that all consumers have their own installations – i.e. if they are all downstream of the same grid distribution transformer - and linked together as a legal entity. It is in this type of self-consumption that NEON makes the most sense, bringing greater efficiency to generation due to the implementation of different consumption patterns in the model that conforms to the community.

The **DSO must ensure**, as required by the EU, **transparent and non-discriminatory conditions** for the implementation of these self-consumption processes, also through the **installation and the exploitation of smart meters**. Furthermore, the **DSO must establish a contract with the legal entity representing collective self-consumers**, to identify all the actors involved and determine how the energy produced is shared among participants.

In 2018, Commission de Régulation de l'Énergie - CRE presented a deliberation with its recommendations and guidelines on the self-consumption-related subject, that seek to:

- **enable the optimal, simplified, and controlled growth of renewable energy self-consumption** to meet energy transition goals at the best price for the community;
- **ensure compliance** with necessary rules so that the electricity system functions properly and safely.

In 2020, a total capacity of 414 MW for self-consumption is ensured by 95,000 PV installations. 78,000 of them inject energy in the grid, whereas 17,000 do not. Installations between 0 and 6 kWp are 95% of the total, representing 72% of the capacity of those that inject power on the grid.

⁸ LOI n° 2017-227 du 24 février 2017 ratifiant les ordonnances n° 2016-1019 du 27 juillet 2016 relative à l'autoconsommation d'électricité et n° 2016-1059 du 3 août 2016 relative à la production d'électricité à partir d'énergies renouvelables et visant à adapter certaines dispositions relatives aux réseaux d'électricité et de gaz et aux énergies renouvelables: <https://bit.ly/3vBGYq0>

FIG. 15 - Analysis of the French self-consumption photovoltaic park

Source: France Territoire Solaire: <https://bit.ly/3sZsCOG>

● **Demand-response market in France**

The French DR market is today one of the most advanced in Europe. DR Aggregators (or OE for Opérateurs d’Effacement) can participate both in Energy and Capacity markets, as shown by the following figure.

FIG. 16 – Different demand response markets available in France

DIFFERENT DEMAND RESPONSE MARKETS

ENERGY	ENERGY	CAPACITY	CAPACITY
Balancing market (MA)	Wholesale market (NEBEF)	Capacity mechanism (MECAPA)	Service Systems (SSy)
Participation through bids on day-ahead. Paid as bid system	Only for Demand-Response operators. Possibility to access the wholesale market for any activation of demand-response	Since 2016. Allow to valorize the capacities to suppliers that need to balance themselves. Take over former public tenders	Through contractualisation of capacities – needs to be very flexible and reactive as action is done on a very fast basis (seconds)

Source: Image processed by SIF

Since 2020, ancillary services markets have been opened to demand response mechanisms, even if still limited to a maximum of 10 MW, allowing DR operators to access balancing and ancillary services (primary and tertiary reserves), the capacity markets and most notably the wholesale day-ahead market, competing directly with unity of production of energy despite

significant entry barriers. This last opportunity is essential since the balancing market alone is very competitive and smaller, as new technologies (e.g., electric vehicles or storage units) are included.

A widely used option is the **Block Exchange Notification of Demand Response mechanism, known as "NEBEF"**. It allows consumers to directly participate in energy markets through load reductions, in exchange for remuneration. Sites can be remunerated based on capacity (fixed premium in €/MW) – providing “available time” where they modulate power generation or decrease consumption –, or energy (in €/MWh) – being paid following effective activation (generation or load reduction) for a fixed power and duration.

All consumption sites may participate either directly – becoming a demand response aggregator (DRA) – if the site has a minimum load reduction capacity of 100 kW, or **indirectly**, through a third-party DR aggregator. In this second case, the consumption site is rewarded according to the terms defined in the contract with the aggregator. The figure below shows the process of NEBEF.

FIG. 17 – Contracting and remuneration in NEBEF

Source: Le Réseau de Transport d'Électricité (RTE): <https://bit.ly/3KCE4py>

Among the key points in the NEBEF rules, notice:

- **aggregators can use the data gathered** through their own metering devices for settlement purposes. These data can be audited by the TSO afterwards;
- the **actual consumption is compared against a predefined consumption baseline**, to establish the amount of curtailed power.

DR aggregators must compensate consumers for the curtailed power as well as electricity suppliers for the unsold electricity. The benefit for erased consumers is only energy saving. This

represents **one of the economic barriers preventing DR actors to participate in the market** since they cannot compete au pair with producers. Directive EU 2019/944 guarantees that such barrier to entry should be removed if it is implemented correctly by the Member States.

Furthermore, to promote the development of electricity load reductions to contribute to the French Multiannual Energy Programme objectives, under Article L271.4 of the French Energy Code, **demand response calls for tenders have been set**. As stated by RTE, **candidates selected** following each call for tenders **are designated by the Minister** in charge of Energy. By contracting via these calls, **participants undertake to provide their demand response capacity for a minimum availability period** for the balancing mechanism and/or NEBEF mechanism. They are awarded a contract with RTE, under the conditions of the specifications for the call for tenders concerned, to receive remuneration for their demand response capacities. Each call for tenders has two lots:

- **Lot 1**, reserved for sites with a contract power less than or equal to 1 MVA (low voltage) and 1 MW (HVA);
- **Lot 2**, reserved for sites with a contract power greater than or equal to 1 MVA (low voltage) and 1 MW (HVA).

By 2022, the **maximum volume that can be contracted for the demand response call for tenders is 7,940 MW**, of which **3,750 MW is reserved for subscribed power sites of 1 MW or less**. The volume of demand response bids selected at the call for tenders 2022 was 2,403 MW, showing a **significant increase for the second consecutive year** (+76% with respect to 2021).

Energy efficiency in buildings in France

According to ODYSSEE-MURE, in 2019 energy consumption of the building sector in France was divided as follow: 65% from space heating, 19% from electric appliances, 10% from water heating and 5% from cooking.

Energy efficiency policies in existing buildings lead to an **8% drop in space heating consumption**, with respect to 2000, despite a slowdown since 2013, with consumption standing at around 10.5 koe/m². Energy consumption for **water heating and cooking decreased by -0.2%/year** and 0.9%/year respectively. The one related to **electrical appliances** rose from 5.5 Mtoe to 7.7 Mtoe **(+1.8%/year)** due to an increasing number of connected devices.

Energy savings between 2000 and 2019 (16.5 Mtoe) **more than offset the increase in residential buildings energy consumption**, leading to an overall reduction of -0.6 Mtoe. Two drivers contributed to the aforementioned increase: a higher number of dwellings (+8.1 Mtoe) and changes in lifestyles (+4.2 Mtoe related to more appliances per dwelling and +0.6 Mtoe related to larger homes).

In 2020, as part of its Plan Relance and given its priority on renovating buildings to align with greener standards, **France updated its thermal regulation** to increase its impact in reducing buildings' GHG emissions and decrease energy consumption. The first thermal building code was

implemented in 1974 and was updated six times before this last one, the **RT2020**. The regulation aims to **reduce energy consumption, increase thermal insulation, decarbonise energy systems, and make greater use of renewable energy**. Specific measures include reviewing buildings' energy performance forbidding future instalment or replacement of fuel oil boilers, implementing mandatory energy reduction consumption standards, and harmonising criteria to incentivise buildings' renovation. RT2020 is built on RT2012, focused on energy in-use requirements, and sets new objectives for a project to receive planning permission. Furthermore, the new regulation defines specific indicators on three strategic categories: energy use, carbon emissions and summer comfort. According to the proposed regulation, **in 2031, the carbon emission thresholds will be reduced on average by 52% with respect to 2022** (Architects Can! 2021).

As of today, about 75% of French building stock has no building code, underlying a **huge potential for energy efficiency intervention**, and making these buildings one of the priorities of the climate roadmap. Energy savings goals were set in the Energy Transition Act in 2015⁹:

- **28% reduction in final energy consumption in 2050**, with respect to the 2012 level;
- **refurbishment of 500,000 existing dwellings each year**, half of which should be occupied by vulnerable consumers.

These objectives can be reached thanks to a mix of regulations, incentives, and public support both for residential and commercial buildings, such as:

- **Building codes “RT 2020”**, implementing the principle of Positive Energy Buildings (PEB) and thus requiring that all the new buildings produce more energy than the consumed one (i.e., primary energy consumption must be lower than a threshold 100 kWh/m²/year for all end-users, varying by climate zone).
- **Building codes**, requiring that all the buildings with a surface area higher than 1000m² meet a global energy performance target. Concerning other residential buildings, minimum performance levels for elements replaced or installed are required by the element-by-element thermal regulation (called RT element).

Legal development of some energy efficiency services in France

Energy policies in France evolve every year. An important step for the regulation of the energy market is represented by the implementation of the EPBD. With the aim to replicate the successful transposition of Directive 91/2002/EC, France has been working on implementing Directive 2010/31/EU since 2010. Law n. 2010-788 and the regulation that followed have significantly improved the energy performance certification process, while the implementation of the new thermal regulation, RT 2012, has brought energy efficiency of new buildings to NZEB level.

In 2015, France embarked on a path of energy transition with the adoption of Law n. 2015-992 (the Law on Energy Transition), establishing new rules supporting renewable energy production

⁹ For more information: <https://bit.ly/36P1kBQ>

and setting out ambitious objectives, which were specified in multi-annual energy program for the period 2016 - 2023. This program aims to increase renewable electricity production from 102 to 113 gigawatts in 2028, twice as much as in 2017. In particular, Power to Hydrogen (P2H2) is among France's tools to support this transition to renewable energies. It is an alternative that could provide flexibility to an electrical system mainly based on renewable energies.

Moreover, the law on Energy Transition has set the target of 2 million electric vehicles to be in use by 2025, and 5 million by 2030. By 2030, this will require 7 million charging stations, most of which will be connected to users' homes.

Following the Clean Energy for all Europeans package, Law n. 2019-1147 on energy and climate has transposed part of it and should be completed by several ordinances, since it was up to Member States to specify the terms of collective self-consumption in their jurisdictions.

Law n. 2019-1147 dated 8 November 2019 on energy and climate deals with a number of subjects, mainly:

- reduction of pollution by capping CO2 emissions for coal-fired power plants. The remaining four coal-fired power plants should close by 2022;
- reinforcement of energy efficiency in buildings;
- achievement of carbon neutrality by 2050 and of the goal of halving the share of nuclear sources by 2035;
- tackle energy-saving certificate fraud by speeding up of processes and strengthening controls.

Moreover, Law n. 2019-1147 transposed the concept of renewable energy community. Through this law, France provided a basic definition for renewable energy communities in Article L211-3-2 of the French Energy Code generally taking over the definitions of the REDII.

Collective self-consumption is further regulated by Article L315-2 of the French Energy Code. According to this article, the self-consumption operation is collective when the electricity supply is made between one or several producers and one or several consumers, gathered through a legal person.

In 2019, also Law n. 2019-1428 on mobility guidelines was adopted to foster the deployment of electric vehicles and set the objective of increasing the number of public charging stations fivefold by 2022.

The year 2020 marked a real change, with ordinance n. 2020-866 that finalised the transposition of provisions on the energy performance of buildings and promotion renewable energy sources and the development of RE2020 (Environmental Regulation 2020). The RE2020 succeeds the R.T. 2012 (Thermal Regulation 2012): with it, we no longer refer only to energy performance, but also to environmental performance.

Authorizations required for the installation of photovoltaic panels

For what concern ground-mounted solar panels, an authorization may or may not be required depending on the height of the structure and its peak power (i.e., the maximum power delivered by the panel).

Authorizations

Height of the structure	Less than 3 kW	Between 3 and 250 kW	Over 250 kW
Up to 1.80 m	Exempted from any formality	Prior declaration of work (DP)	Planning permission
Over 1.80 m	Prior declaration of work (DP)		

Authorization is necessary also when installing ground-mounted solar panels in the following areas: heritage sites, surroundings of a historic monument; classified sites; nature reserves; areas intended to be classified in the heart of a future national park; areas inside delimited national parks. If the peak power of the installation is less than 3 kW, a DP is sufficient. Above 3 kW, it is necessary to apply for a planning permission.

For what concern the installation of photovoltaic panels on the roof of a building, it is necessary to send to the town hall a request for a DP regardless of the surface area of these panels. It takes at least one month from the submission of the application to obtaining the permit.

This period increases to 2 months if the panels will be installed on a building in a protected area (e.g. towns, villages or districts whose conservation, restoration, rehabilitation or enhancement is of public interest from a historical, architectural, archaeological, artistic or landscape point of view; natural sites and monuments whose conservation or preservation is of general interest from the artistic, historical, scientific, legendary or picturesque point of view; nature reserves, areas intended to be classified in the heart of a future national park and the heart of delimited national parks). The DP is valid for 3 years.

ITALY

A quick overview of the targets set by the Italian National Energy and Climate Plan is useful to introduce this chapter. The Italian integrated NECP largely builds on the 2017 Italian Energy Strategy and is intended to implement a vision of broad economic transformation, in which decarbonisation, energy efficiency and renewable energy sources priorities contribute to the objectives of a more environmentally friendly economy. In particular, Italy's 2030 main targets are:

- **-43% in primary energy consumption** compared to the PRIMES 2007 scenario;
- **30% of renewable energy** in gross final energy consumption, in particular 22% in the transport sector;
- **-33% of GHG emissions** for all non-ETS sectors compared to 2005

The Plan also describes macroeconomic impact, in addition to health, environmental, employment and education, skills and social impacts, including fair transition aspects (in terms of costs and benefits) of the planned policies and described measures¹⁰.

Wholesale and retail electricity markets in Italy

The electricity supply chain is divided into **four segments: production, transmission, distribution, and sale**. Terna, the Italian TSO (Transmission System Operator) and ISO (Independent System Operator), acts as a monopolist on government concession, and its main activities are the transmission and dispatching of electricity.

FIG. 18 - The supply chain of the national electricity system

Source: TERNA: <https://bit.ly/3t4XLAs>

The **spread of RES**, combined with the **reduction of thermoelectric generation** and the **electrification of consumption** are the **three main factors that have characterised the evolution of the electricity system** in Italy in recent years, supporting its progressive decarbonisation. In 2021, the **installed capacity of RES in Italy exceeds 56 GW**, due above all to the increase in the last decade of non-programmable sources (solar and wind in the first place) (Energy & Strategy 2021).

¹⁰ Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan in Italy: <https://bit.ly/3HH5TuS>

FIG. 19 - Total power installed from RES

Source: Energy & Strategy 2021: <https://bit.ly/34zQU8s>

The wholesale market in Italy

The electricity market was born following the Legislative Decree of 16 March 1999, n. 79 ("Bersani Decree"), which transposes the EU directive on the creation of an internal energy market (Directive 96/92/EC replaced by Directive 2003/54/EC).

The electricity market is divided into:

- Day Ahead Market (Mercato del Giorno Prima - MGP);
- Intraday market (Mercato Intragioraliero - MI);
- Daily products market (Mercato dei prodotti giornalieri - MPEG);
- Dispatching service market (Mercato del servizio di dispacciamento – MSD).

The Day Ahead Market (MGP) hosts most of the electricity trading transactions. On the MGP, **hourly blocks of energy are exchanged for the following day¹¹**. Operators participate in submitting offers indicating the quantity and the maximum/minimum price they are willing to pay/receive.

The **offers are accepted once the market session is closed** since the MGP is an auction market and not a continuous trading market. The price is determined, for each hour, by the intersection of the supply and demand curve and differs from area to area.

Accepted purchase offers referring to consumption units belonging to the Italian geographical areas are valued at the **single national price (Prezzo Nazionale Unico - PUN)**, equal to the average of the prices of the geographical areas weighted by the quantities purchased in these areas. In Italy, "Gestore del Mercato Energetico" (GME) acts as a central counterparty.

¹¹ MGP opens at 8.00 on the ninth day before the day of delivery and closes at 12.00 on the day before the day of delivery. The results of the MGP are communicated by 12.58 on the day before the day of delivery.

FIG. 20 – Interconnected areas

Source: TERNA – Allegato A.24 al Codice di rete individuazione zone della rete rilevante (dal 1 gennaio 2021): <https://bit.ly/3t4XLAs>

The Intraday Market (MI) allows operators to change the programs defined in the MGP through **additional offers to buy or sell**. Trading on the MI takes place through the conduct of three MI-A auction sessions and one MI-XBID continuous trading session.

In the **MI-A auction sessions**¹², at the same time as the negotiation of the buy and sale offers, the intraday interconnection capacity is allocated between all the areas of the Italian market and the other geographic areas interconnected to the same involved in the Market Coupling. The buy and sale offers are selected based on the same criterion described for MGP, i.e., merit and technical feasibility.

The **continuous MI-XBID** session is divided into three phases¹³, in the context of which, at the same time as the negotiation of the purchase and sale offers, the intraday interconnection capacity is allocated between all the areas of the Italian market and the other geographic areas interconnected to the same active in the XBID. The MI-A auction sessions and the trading phases

¹² The session of the MI-A1, which takes place after the closing of the MGP, opens at 12.55 on the day before the day of delivery and closes at 15.00 on the same day. The results of the MI-A1 are communicated by 3.30 pm of the day before the day of delivery.

The MI-A2 session opens at 12.55 on the day before the delivery day and closes at 22.00 on the same day. The results of the MI-A2 are communicated by 10.30 pm of the day before the day of delivery.

The MI-A3 session opens at 12.55 on the day before the delivery day and closes at 10.00 on the delivery day. The results of the MI-A3 are communicated by 10.30 on the day of delivery.

¹³ The MI-XBID phase I session opens at 15.30 on day D-1 and closes at 21.40 on day D-1.

The phase II MI-XBID session opens at 10.30 pm on day D-1 and closes:

- for the relevant periods corresponding to the first twelve hours of day D, one hour before the start of each relevant period (h-1);
- for the relevant periods corresponding to the second twelve hours of day D, at 09.40 am of day D.

The phase III MI-XBID session opens from 10.30 on day D and closes one hour before the start of each relevant period (h-1). Bids and offers can be submitted per unit and per portfolio.

of the MI-XBID session take place in a sequential and non-overlapping manner. Also in this case, GME acts as a central counterparty.

The Daily Products Market (MPEG) is the venue for the **negotiation of daily products, on a continuous basis, with the obligation to deliver energy**. All operators in the electricity market are automatically admitted to the MPEG. On the MPEG daily products are tradable with unit price differential¹⁴ (with respect to PUN) or full unit price¹⁵. Both baseload and peak load profiles are negotiable on the MPEG.

Those who can buy and sell daily products on the MPEG are the electricity market operators who are also operators on the energy accounts platform (Piattaforma dei Conti Energia - PCE) and are enabled to record transactions on their own electricity accounts. Net energy delivery position resulting from the negotiation of the daily products traded on the MPEG is recorded in corresponding transactions on the PCE in accordance with the procedures set out in the electricity market rules (GME 2003). GME always acts as a central counterparty. MPEG sessions take place on weekdays.

The Dispatching Service Market (MSD) is where Terna procures the necessary **resources for the management and control of the system** (resolution of intra-zone congestion, creation of the energy reserve, balancing in real-time). On the MSD, Terna acts as a central counterparty and accepted offers are remunerated at the price presented (pay-as-bid). The MSD is divided into the programming phase (ex-ante MSD) and Balancing Market ("Mercato del Bilanciamento" - MB). Both segments are active in several sessions, in accordance with the provisions of the dispatching regulations. The Balancing Market consists of the continuous presentation of offers, with timetable details for each of the 24 hours.

The retail market in Italy

From 1 July 2019, Law no. 124/2017 ("*Legge annuale per il mercato e la concorrenza*") established the **end of the price protection** provided by the Italian Authority (Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente - ARERA) **both for electricity and natural gas**. For the electricity sectors, this applies to domestic customers and low voltage connected small companies. The original deadline was postponed in 2019, with different timing for different categories.

The deadline for all the **small enterprises and some micro-enterprises**¹⁶ has been set for 1 January 2021. For the remaining micro-enterprises not included in the description, the deadline will be 1 January 2023. Families and domestic consumers will have to shift to a liberalised market by 10 January 2024 but already have the right to switch and decide which seller and which type of contract to choose, selecting the offer deemed most suitable for their needs.

¹⁴ The price indicated in the formulation of the offers and therefore the price that is determined at the end of the negotiation phase is the expression of the differential, with respect to the PUN, at which operators are willing to negotiate such products.

¹⁵ The price indicated in the formulation of the offers and therefore the price that is determined at the end of the negotiation phase is the expression of the unitary exchange value of electricity covered by the negotiated contracts.

¹⁶ Those with less than 10 employees and annual turnover not exceeding €2 million

To support the transition and to improve the understanding and participation of end customers, some important **obligations have been introduced for sellers** by the Ministry of Economic Development and the Authority, including:

- **standard offers** for end-consumers (PLACET offers).

The Offers Portal has been online since 1 July 2018, for the collection and publication in open data mode of all the offers on the electricity retail market. The Offer Portal is aimed to enhance the comparability of energy service offers for families and small businesses.

- the establishment of the **Electricity Vendor List**.

All electricity sellers must necessarily be registered in a list, which will be established by decree by the Ministry of Economic Development, as required by Law 124/2017 (art. 1, paragraphs 80-81). At the moment, an operator database exists on the ARERA website.

- **monitoring of retail markets**.

- preparation of **guidelines to promote commercial offers in favour of purchasing groups**.

Law 124/2017 provides a series of interventions to support the competitiveness of the retail market and the active participation of end customers.

To reduce the cost of electricity bills, the Authority prepares guidelines to promote commercial offers of electricity in favour of purchasing groups, with particular reference to comparability, transparency and the advertising of offers, as well as the creation of IT platforms aimed at facilitating the aggregation of small consumers (Article 1, paragraph 65).

● **Self-consumption in Italy**

- a. **In the last years, an interesting regulatory framework on collective self-consumption has emerged in Italy. Until recently, self-consumption was mainly possible through SAP self-consumption models (Legislative Decree n. 79/1999) and SEU efficiency systems (Legislative Decree n. 115/2008): collective self-consumption was not possible until related legislation was updated on several occasions.**

In February 2020, art. 42-bis of the law 8/2020 (*Decreto Milleproroghe*) the **pilot phase of transposition of the Renewable Energy Directive 2018/2001 (RED II)** on energy communities and collective self-consumption has been launched. The pilot phase is valid from 1 March 2020 up to 60 days following the definitive transposition of the RED II Directive. Article 42-bis introduces for the first time into Italian legislation the **definitions of "Renewable energy self-consumers acting collectively" and "Renewable Energy Community"** and defines the guidelines on which they must be based and the subsequent regulatory measures of ARERA, Ministry of Economic Development (MiSE) and GSE.

The decree defines the **potential members of collective self-consumers schemes** (final customers, and for subjects other than households only if the participation does not constitute the main commercial or professional activity) **and of renewable energy communities** (individuals, SMEs, territorial bodies or local authorities, whose participation in the renewable energy community does not constitute the main commercial and industrial activity).

The decree also defines "**shared energy**" as the minimum, in each hourly period, between the electricity produced and fed into the grid by the renewable source plants part of the configuration and the electricity taken from all the associated end customers.

In addition to the decree, renewable energy communities are regulated by the implementation measures of ARERA's resolution 318/2020/R/EEL and the Ministry of Economic Development's DM 16 September 2020. The resolution regulates, among other things, financial compensation for the electricity used in the collective self-consumption systems, also by setting amounts payable by GSE as compensation for these systems.

Through the 2019-2020 European delegation law of 22 April 2021, the Italian Parliament delegated the Government to implement some European directives, including the Internal Electricity Market Directive 2019/944 (IEM) and the Renewable Energy Directive 2018/2001. Final implementing decrees include a variation in the definition of "shared energy":

Shared energy is equal to the minimum, in each hourly period, between the electricity produced and fed into the grid by the plants and the electricity withdrawn by all the associated final customers **within the portion of the distribution grid underlying the same market area**. Energy **can also be shared through storage facilities**, and the electricity generation and storage facilities being shared must be in the availability and control of the community.

The perimeter of the definition, therefore, is extended to the energy exchanged in the same market area. However, the application of the incentives is limited only to a subset of this energy, according to the provisions of articles 5 and 8 of the legislative decree transposing the RED II directive.

Indeed, Article 5 states that "for **plants with power equal to or less than 1 MW** belonging to energy communities or collective self-consumption configurations, it is possible to access a direct incentive that rewards, through a specific tariff, which can also be graduated based on the power of the plants, self-consumed energy instantly».

Looking in details at the configurations, main innovations are introduced with respect to the pilot phase.

Renewable energy communities:

- the potential members are **all final customers and businesses whose participation is not the main commercial and industrial activity**;
- control power belongs exclusively to: "**individuals, SMEs, territorial bodies and local authorities, including municipal administrations, research and training bodies, religious bodies, third sector and environmental protection organisations [...]**, located in the territory of the same Municipalities where the production plants are located";
- **existing plants can join the community**, to an extent **not exceeding 30% of the total power of the production plants** belonging to the community;
- **extended range of possible activities**, including the possibility of **exploiting other forms of RES**, promoting **integrated home automation and energy efficiency interventions**,

offering recharging services of electric vehicles to its members, assume the role of retail company and offer ancillary and flexibility services. Providing environmental, economic or social benefits to the members or to the local areas in which the REC operates remains mandatory.

Renewable self-consumers:

- **partial expansion of the configuration:** production plants may be located in buildings or in sites other than those where the self-consumer operates, as long as they are available to the consumer himself. Self-consumers must all be in the same building or condominium anyway;
- renewable energy self-consumers who act collectively, in addition to selling self-produced energy, can offer **ancillary and flexibility services, possibly through an aggregator**.

The concept of active customers, active customers acting collectively, and CECs was established respectively in Article 15 and Article 16 of the Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944. As of December 2021, Italy has adopted all major provisions in the national legislation, with a legislative decree scheme awaiting publication in the Official Gazette, allowing active consumers. The awaited legislative decree establishes the framework for CECs.

- b. [By decree of 16 September 2020, the Ministry of Economic Development has introduced support tariffs to encourage the development of the self-consumption model: collective self-consumption is eligible for an incentive of €100/MWh on self-consumed energy. For energy communities, the incentive will be increased to €110/MWh to compensate for the higher fees associated with this system. The incentive is granted for a period of 20 years.](#)

In the meantime, GSE has issued technical rules regulating the incentivisation of self-consumption and energy communities and launched a web portal through which applications for the allocation of incentives are to be submitted. **In 2020, in Italy, there were 740.000 self-consumption units, accounting for a total installed capacity of 26 GW;** these facilities generated 28 TWh per year and covered around 9% of the total electricity consumption.

Active consumers
End customers have the right to participate in the market as active customers. They can sell self-produced electricity and participate – directly or through an aggregator – in the day-ahead market, intraday market and balancing markets. They can assign the management of the plants to third parties. Active customers are financially responsible for the imbalances they bring to the electricity grid and for balancing (or can delegate their responsibility to third parties).
Active consumers acting collectively

Active clients who act collectively regulate relations through a private law contract, which also identifies a responsible party. The production and storage plants must be located in sites related to the active customers themselves. Ownership and management may be held by a third party, subject to the instructions of one or more active customers belonging to the group.

Citizens Energy Community

CEC is a private law entity that can take on any legal form, with the main purpose of pursuing environmental, economic, or social benefits in favour of the members or of the territory in which it operates.

Members of the CEC regulate their relations through a private law contract, and identify a responsible person (which can be the community itself, a member of it or a third party).

The community can generate, consume, store, distribute and supply electricity, be an aggregator, provide energy efficiency services, electric vehicle charging services or other energy services, and is responsible for the distribution of the electricity shared between its participants.

The sharing of the electricity produced by CECs can **exploit the existing distribution network or**, in the presence of specific technical reasons, **through lease or purchase of portions of the network or via newly built networks**. Networks managed by CECs are considered public networks with third party connection obligations (public network whose operation is the subject of a concession), regardless of the ownership of the network.

According to the analysis carried out by Energy & Strategy Group (2021), as regards collective self-consumption, **two main clusters have emerged in Italy**. In both, the **RES plant is always installed on a residential or business building (SME) and it is physically connected to the common utilities of the building itself** (connection to the distribution network is not required). The initiatives are mainly financed through the assignment of credit associated with tax deductions and there is a contextual implementation of energy efficiency measures for the building.

FIG. 21 - Collective self-consumption clusters in Italy

	CLUSTER 1 PUBLIC ENTITIES AND THIRD SECTOR	CLUSTER 2 ENERGY PLAYER
Initiator	Local municipality and other public or non-profit bodies	Energy player
Value proposition	Reducing energy expenditure, reducing energy poverty, supporting RES	Business opportunities, promoting energy efficiency
Members	Citizens and SMEs	Citizens and SMEs
Investment	Assignment of credit/invoice discount and possibly public fundings	Transfer of credit/invoice discount, investment by the initiator
Distribution of economic benefits	Either all to the members or a small part to the group itself	Partly to the energy player and partly to members

Source: Image processed by SIF

In **Cluster 1 ("Public bodies and third sector")**, public bodies or non-profit cooperatives are the starters of the initiatives. These subjects do not participate directly as members of the aggregate but rather act as "catalysts" of the initiatives, also delegating to the members of the aggregate financing the initiatives themselves, possibly supporting them for some accessory cost items (technical consultancy, or measurement devices and platforms). The main purpose is to mitigate energy poverty in the area and to guarantee the necessary tools to favour the diffusion of renewable resources. On the other side, **Cluster 2 ("Energy Player")** shows the presence of an industrial player with technical knowledge and financial capacity to promote the development of collective self-consumption initiatives. Unlike energy communities, in this case, the promoter may be a construction company that builds new condominium housing units or renovates existing buildings. In both cases, the investment is supported by the residents, who have access to tax deductions and implement energy efficiency interventions. This configuration is the most widespread today.

Regarding CECs, again according to Energy & Strategy Group analysis, there exist three main clusters. **Cluster 1 ("Public bodies and third sector")** is the most widespread and is based on the direct relationship between citizens and the local public body (with the latter acting as a "catalyst" of the initiative) and on the possibility of benefiting grants and subsidies. This model tends to be

rigid due to the predominant role of public administration. In **Cluster 2 ("Energy player")**, there is a player of the energy sector which often involves the local municipality to exploit the knowledge it has of the territory as well as its direct contact with citizens. The investment in RES may be fully made by the energy player or involving citizens and SMEs (which can benefit from tax deductions). Technical skills are ensured by the energy player, favouring the scalability of the initiative. In **Cluster 3 ("Private citizens")** the investment is fully supported by citizens and SMEs, who take advantage of tax deductions and subsidised loans. This Cluster is less structured and its economic benefits are divided amongst the members of the community. Despite this, it appears to be the least widespread configuration since citizens/SMEs must support the entire investment and they have to discover the opportunity on their own.

FIG. 22 - CECs clusters in Italy

	CLUSTER 1 PUBLIC ENTITIES AND THIRD SECTOR	CLUSTER 2 ENERGY PLAYER	CLUSTER 3 PRIVATE CITIZENS / SMEs
Initiator	Local municipality and other public or non-profit bodies	Energy player	Group members (citizens and SMEs)
Value proposition	Generating value in the area, reducing energy poverty, reducing energy expenditure	Business opportunities, promoting energy efficiency	Reduce energy expenditure, contribute to environmental sustainability
Members	Citizens and SMEs, PA utilities	Citizens, SMEs, PA utilities	Citizens and SMEs
Investment	Public funding, foundations/banks	Investment by the initiator, investment by the group members	Investment by the group members
Distribution of economic benefits	Either all to the members or a small part to the group itself	Partly to the energy player and partly to members	All members

Source: Image processed by SIF

Energy communities and collective self-consumption in the Italian Recovery and Resilience Plan

The Italian Recovery and Resilience Plan (Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza - PNRR) set €2.2 billion to install 2 GW of renewable plants in collective self-consumption configurations and energy communities, to promote renewables and self-consumption and to support the economy of areas at risk of depopulation (small municipalities and internal areas).

The resources are invested with zero-interest loans covering up to 100% of the eligible costs (maximum duration of 10 years) to build the plants and are divided as follows:

- €1,600 million to RECs;
- €600 million for collective self-consumption.

The recipients of the measure will be public administrations, private citizens, and SMEs in municipalities with less than 5,000 inhabitants. The power limit of 200 kW (later raised by the scheme of legislative decree implementing the RED II) is maintained for incentivized plants, and they must come into operation no later than 2026¹⁷.

The resources provided by the PNRR cannot be combined with the incentives of RES 1 (Ministerial Decree of 4 July 2019), while they are combined with the incentives for collective self-consumption and for CECs in force.

Demand-response market in Italy

The growing share of load covered by non-programmable RES (solar and wind), as well as the reduced electricity demand due also to efficiency improvements, posed growing difficulties to TERNA which faced the **necessity to ensure increasing flexibility on the Market for the Dispatching Service**, where ancillary services are offered.

On 25 July 2019 ARERA published a document for consultation – 322/2019/R/EEL – on a new integrated text of electricity dispatching (Testo Integrato del Dispacciamento Elettrico - TIDE). Among the main objectives, the document aimed to review consumers' participation in the markets and planning of units allowed to provide ancillary services. TIDE reviews:

- **currently existing ancillary services and the related procurement and remuneration methods** (as well as the possible definition of new ancillary services);
- **definition of the methods through which RES, storage systems, distributed generation and demand-side can provide the necessary resources** (also via aggregation);
- **revision of the regulation regarding imbalances.**

The report analyses in detail the experiments currently underway regarding the opening of the MSD as well as the definition of new services (such as experimentation on the ultra-fast frequency reserves).

Regarding implicit DR schemes, the **main one implemented in Italy is the Time of Use (ToU) tariff**. Pre-set prices, reflecting the cost of electricity in different time frames, nudge customers to **adjust their processes shifting consumption from peak hours, reducing load when it is most needed**. This participation works on a voluntary basis.

ToU tariffs represent a primitive approach to implicit DR, being a non-dynamic pricing, as DR should be (Ambience 2020). In Italy, there are two kinds: dual-rate tariff, aimed at residential

¹⁷ In the detailed sheets of the projects, it is specified that there are 5,000 municipalities with less than 5,000 inhabitants, characterised by an estimated annual electricity consumption of 7-8 TWh. It is estimated that the implementation of the incentivized interventions will lead to covering 20% of this demand. Finally, the incentive measure should also lead to 13,300 new temporary jobs and 1,100 new jobs per year.

users. Electricity price is divided into two-time ranges; and triple-rate tariff, aimed at small consumers and small enterprises but excluding residential users.

Looking at explicit DR in Italy, they are allowed only for some types of programs.

On the balancing market, following the approval of Resolution 300/2017, a series of Pilot Projects were launched, with the aim of collecting results and useful evidence for the drafting of the new Integrated Text of Electricity Dispatching (TIDE). The recent initiatives launched in this context concern the provision of the ultra-fast reserves service, secondary frequency regulation and voltage regulation. TERNA identified the most innovative pilot projects as:

- **Virtually Aggregated Consumption Units (UVAC)**, composed only of only consumption units;
- **Virtually Aggregated Production Units (UVAP)**, composed of only non-relevant production units (programmable and non-programmable), including storage systems;
- **Virtually Aggregated Mixed Units (UVAM)**, composed by both non-relevant production units (programmable and non-programmable, including storage systems and EV) and consumption units;
- **Virtually Aggregated Nodal Units (UVAN)**, composed by relevant production units, (voluntary participation), and/or non-relevant production units (programmable and non-programmable), and potentially consumption units under the same node of the electricity network.

These also allow those distributed resources not meeting minimum requirements defined by TERNA to provide ancillary services such as congestion management, balancing and tertiary reserve services (but not secondary reserves).

In February 2021, the ARERA Resolution 70/2021 amended the "Regulation containing the procedures for the creation, qualification and management of UVAM for the dispatching services market" and the "Procurement procedure by term of dispatching resources provided by UVAMs" prepared by Terna, which introduces some new features, including the introduction of tests for assessing the reliability of the aggregates.

As of February 2020, **Terna qualified almost 1,300 MW of UVAM to participate in ancillary services market for the provision of tertiary reserve and balancing service.** The majority of them is represented by large industrial consumption sites, but the number of UVAM made by an aggregation of small consumption points (e.g., domestic consumers) is increasing and is expected to increase further with the deployment of 2G smart meters (MISE 2020).

Italy is one of the EU countries where interruptibility schemes are active. In this context, participating consumers are remunerated for their availability on auctions. In Italy providers also receive payment for the energy interrupted based on pay-as-bid auctions (daily for Italy, where the remuneration per activation is capped at 3,000 euros). The minimum eligible capacity is 1 MW in Italy. In 2020, the Italian scheme contracted the biggest capacity: 4,600 MW/year, 4000 MW for the mainland, 400 MW for Sicily and 200 MW for Sardinia.

Other important measures, in the context of the ecological transition, are those contained in the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, approved on 13 July 2021, which allocates approximately €2.2 billion for the development of energy communities.

Under Legislative Decree n. 199/2021 (the RED II Decree), the Italian government finally implemented the RED II Directive, whereby it completed the framework on renewable energy communities and also set specific authorisation procedures for green hydrogen generation plants, similar to those existing for storage facilities.

Energy efficiency in buildings in Italy

Italy is one of the most energy-efficient countries, with a primary energy intensity approximately 18% lower than the EU average.

According to ENEA Annual Report on energy efficiency 2021 (ENEA 2021), in 2019, the energy consumption of the residential sector was 31.1 Mtoe, down 2.4% compared to the previous year. The reduction concerned the main energy sources except for electricity (+ 0.7%): down natural gas (-2.3%), diesel (-20.9%), heat (-18.7%) and solid biofuels (-0.2%).

FIG. 23 - Final energy consumption in households by type of fuel, 2010 - 2020

Source: Eurostat -Statistics | Eurostat (europa.eu): <https://bit.ly/3Kw3R2q>

Natural gas is the main source of energy with a share of over 50% of the overall consumption of the sector, followed by solid biofuels (20%) and electricity (18%).

The energy consumption of the sector showed an increasing trend until 2010 and then reversed: + 19.5% in the period 1990-2019. In 2019, the share of consumption absorbed by air conditioning

(heating and cooling) was almost 70%, lower than the 2018 share and influenced by the overall increasing temperatures. Energy consumption for lighting and electrical appliances (equal to 13.6% of the total) was stable in 2019 compared to 2018.

One key element is the **Strategy for the Upgrading of National Real Estate** (Strategia per la Riquilificazione del Patrimonio Immobiliare Nazionale - STREPIN). Buildings for residential use amounted to 12.42 million, with almost 32 million homes. Over 65% of this building stock is over 45 years old, that is, it is prior to law no. 373 of 1976, the first law on energy saving. 22% of the heated usable area relates to the construction period prior to 1945 and a further 42% to the 1946-1980 period.

To promote energy efficiency, various **incentive tools are available**: these include **tax deductions for redevelopment interventions**, the **thermal account (“Conto Termico”)** and the **white certificate system**.

- **Thermal account 2.0**

Aimed at public administrations, companies, and individuals, it promotes the increase of energy efficiency and the production of renewable energy. With respect to the first version of 2012, there is an expansion of the methods of access and of the subjects admitted (social cooperatives and cooperatives of inhabitants are also included among the PAs), and new energy efficiency measures are planned. In 2020, €451.2 million of direct access incentives were recognized. The energy efficiency and thermal renewable energy interventions incentivized in direct access in 2020 amounted to 113,498 (ENEA 2021).

- **White certificates**

Securities corresponding to realised energy savings. The system is linked to the achievement of annual objectives by electricity and natural gas distributors. During the year 2021, the GSE recognized a total of 1,120,672 White Certificates (-35% compared to 2020). The certified primary energy savings are equal to 0,396 Mtoe (GSE 2022).

- **National Energy Efficiency Fund**

The Fund supports energy efficiency interventions carried out by companies and by the Public Administration on buildings, plants, and production processes.

- **Superbonus 110%**

The decree n. 34/2020 (*Decreto Rilancio*), converted into law no. 77 of 17 July 2020, introduced the so-called Superbonus: a tax deduction of 110% of the expenses incurred for energy efficiency interventions, which comply with specific conditions, and seismic improvement interventions.

The super bonus is composed by the Ecobonus and the Sismabonus. The bonus aims to stimulate local economies and includes numerous interventions, such as insulation solutions, efficient window frames, replacement of heating and air conditioning systems and installation of renewable energy generation systems. Therefore, when renovating a

building, combining energy efficiency measures with seismic retrofitting is an opportunity to obtain significant incentives.

A key instrument is represented by the **energy performance certificate (Attestato di Prestazione Energetica - APE)**. Since 2015, the new rules on the minimum energy performance requirements of buildings and for the drafting of the APE have been in force.

The decree¹⁸ for the adaptation of the national guidelines for the energy certification of buildings:

- describes the guidelines and the connection between the State and the Regions for the preparation of energy performance certificates;
- establishes an information system for the management of a national cadastre of energy performance certificates and thermal plants, the Information System on Energy Performance Certificates (Sistema Informativo sugli Attestati di Prestazione Energetica - SIAPE)
- introduces the constraint for Regions and Provinces to establish control plans and procedures, to analyse at least 2% per year of the APEs of their own territory.

In November 2020, ENEA published the **SIAPE portal (Information System on Energy Performance Certificates) online to support the dissemination of information** deriving from energy certification and intended for all those involved in the energy requalification chain.

Legal development of some energy efficiency services in Italy

Energy electricity compensation with hydrogen storage during the off PV production period

The Italian regulatory framework regulating hydrogen production, operation, and connection is rather fragmented and often this has proven to be a barrier to the development of new projects.

On 16 December 2016, with Legislative Decree n. 257/2016, the Italian government has transposed European Directive 2014/94/EU for the development of an infrastructure for alternative fuels, which officially included hydrogen.

On 23 October 2018, the Ministerial Decree on “Technical rules of fire prevention for design, construction and operation of hydrogen distribution facilities for automotive vehicles” was issued. Compared to the previous ministerial decree of 2006 regulating the same matter, this Decree has overcome some of the regulatory barriers that affected the construction and operating of hydrogen plants during previous years. The decree also establishes that an applicant wishing to build a new hydrogen production plant must accurately indicate the place where the plant is expected to be built so that the local authorities can assess compatibility with the Land Use Plan.

In November 2020, the Ministry of Economic Development (MISE) published the first “Guidelines for the National Hydrogen Strategy” identifying the sectors in which green hydrogen is expected to become competitive in the short term such as public transportation, chemicals and refining.

¹⁸ Interministerial Decree of 26 June 2015 - Adaptation of national guidelines for the energy certification of buildings. For more information: <https://bit.ly/3IFH83F>

Nevertheless, the MISE guidelines were not followed by the publication of a definitive national strategy. Anyways, the key role of hydrogen in the context of the national energy transition has been enshrined in the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, which also provides for strong economic support to the hydrogen industry.

Finally, Decree-Law n. 36/2022 introduced a series of measures to support the development of the hydrogen market.

Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system optimization and control

Over the years, the Italian regulatory framework and policies on energy efficiency has been shaped by the EU regulatory frameworks.

Specifically, Legislative Decree n. 192/2005, modified by Legislative decree n. 311/2006, set the basis for Directive 2002/91/EC (EPDB) implementation in Italy.

This decree can be considered the fundamental legislative text at national level on energy efficiency in buildings. The decree also regulates the operation and maintenance of HVAC systems.

It was followed by a number of complementary legal acts updating the minimum requirements for buildings, building components and technical building systems, while extending the calculation to cooling and lighting systems and providing guidelines for energy performance certification (2009) and defining requirements for assessors as well as specifications for the inspection of technical building systems (2013).

Subsequently, Law n.90/2013 implemented Directive 2010/31/EU, introducing significant changes to the first 2005 implementation. In June 2015, three inter-ministerial decrees (26 June 2015) have completed the EPBD transposition, which also established stricter minimum requirements for new buildings and major renovations, defined NZEB as well as rules for taking renewable energy sources in buildings into account, and provided new national guidelines for the Energy Performance Contract.

The 2017 Italian National Energy Strategy (thereafter the SEN) confirms the key role of energy efficiency in the country's energy transition plan, building on the measures contained in the Clean Energy for All Europeans package. The same year also saw the adoption of the Guidelines for the preparation, implementation and evaluation of energy efficiency project to access the Italian White Certificates scheme. The mechanism of White Certificates was updated by Ministerial Decree of 11 January 2017 (which introduced a deep redesign of the Italian scheme, affecting many aspects such as targets, baseline and additionality, saving assessment and measurement, verification and control procedures) and supplemented by Ministerial Decree of 10 May 2018 and by Directorial Decree of 30 April 2019 that defined the list of eligible interventions and updated the eligible project types.

Legislative decree 21 May 2021 introduced other reforms, with the aim of addressing a drop in the number of certificates issued by companies and projects submitted and the challenges arising from the COVID-19 pandemic. The National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) introduced important measures for the energy requalification of buildings. Component 3 of the mission 2 on the “green revolution and ecological transition”, dedicated to the energy efficiency and building

renovation, aims to make Italian buildings more efficient and safer, which is an important dimension for reducing consumption and cutting CO2 emissions. These measures also aim to prevent seismic risk for buildings constructed in past decades. For this objective, some €15 billion have been earmarked. Finally, in order to respond to the challenges of the energy transition and decarbonisation, as well as to the current increase in the price of electricity and gas, article 9, paragraph 1 of Law Decree n. 17/2022 provides for measures to simplify and provide maximum incentives for the construction of plants for the production of energy from renewable sources, with specific reference to solar plants, both thermal and photovoltaic. Law n. 34/2022 clarifies that article 9 of Law Decree n.17/2022 applies also to historical centres. Even in these parts of cities, the installation of solar panels on buildings or other structures is free and does not require prior consent. The installation of solar panels is subject to municipal authorisation only for “Buildings and Areas of Notable Public Interest” which are subject to landscape restrictions pursuant to Article 136, paragraph 1, letter c) of Legislative Decree n. 42/2004 “Code of Cultural and Landscape Heritage.” However, Law n. 34/2022 specified that, even for buildings located in historical centres that are subject to constraints, the installation is free if it takes place with “panels integrated in the roofs that are not visible from outdoor public spaces and panoramic viewpoints, except for roofs whose coverings are made of traditional local materials.”

EV charging from clean resources

ARERA started dealing with e-mobility in 2010 and launched several pilot projects aimed at developing electric vehicle charging infrastructure. The aim was to trigger the opening of the chargers, but also to remove any possible regulatory or tariff disturbances observed in the implementation of those projects.

In Italy until 2010, there was no regulatory framework for e-mobility, and for that reason ARERA decided to launch a tender for demonstration projects in order to develop infrastructure for charging stations in public spaces, with a view to finding effective and competitive solutions for this new activity. The ARG/ELT 242/10 decision defines the selection criteria and incentives for the next five years.

On 14 January 2017, Legislative Decree n. 257/2016 – known as the DAFI (Directive Alternative Fuel Initiative) came into force in Italy. The DAFI implements at the national level the Directive 2014/94/EU, on the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure. The main objective of the decree is to reduce the dependence on oil and mitigate the environmental impact in the transport sector. Art. 4 specifies that by 31 December 2020, an adequate number of charging points accessible to the public must be set up to ensure inter-operability between existing points and any to be installed and, depending on market needs, that electric vehicles are able to operate in urban and suburban agglomerations at least.

Furthermore, according to the DAFI, by 31 December 2017, municipalities had to update their building regulations to meet requirements on the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure. From 1 June 2017, new buildings and those that have been significantly renovated must provide connection points for EV recharging.

On 6 February 2016, the PNIRE – National Infrastructure Plan for the recharging of electric-powered vehicles was published. PNIRE focusses on the construction of infrastructural networks for the charging of electrically powered vehicles. It was drawn up with the aim of defining specific guidelines to guarantee the unitary development of e-charging services at a national level. Subsequently, the Ministerial Decree of 3 August 2017 identifies the declarations, certificates, affidavits, and technical documents to be submitted, as well as the SCIA concerning the construction of charging infrastructure for electric vehicles.

Finally, the Italian government provides some subsidies or tax incentives to motivate construction or operation of charging stations. Pursuant to the Decree of the Prime Minister of 1 February 2018, state financed a share for the construction of recharging columns. Moreover, a tax deduction was introduced in 2019 for the construction of charging points for electric vehicles for private use.

It should be noted that incentive mechanisms are also provided for the purchase of electric vehicles. According to the Budget Law 2019, as amended by Law Decree n. 162/2019, for those who register a new electric vehicle of category M1 (intended for the transport of persons, with a maximum of eight seats in addition to the driver's seat) a contribution of up to €6,000 is available. In this regard, the most recent measure is Legislative Decree n.17/2022. The decree establishes funds for the reconversion of the Italian automotive industry amounting to €700 million in 2022 and €1 billion per year from 2023 to 2030. Most of these funds, i.e. €650 million for 2022, 2023 and 2024 each (for the remaining years up to 2030 the allocation will be decided later), will be earmarked to finance the purchase of "green" vehicles.

SPAIN

To introduce the Spanish regulations of electricity market it's important to stress that also the Spanish integrated National Energy and Climate Plan lays the foundation for a carbon neutral economy by 2050; while covering all dimensions, this NECP is particularly comprehensive on targets and contributions as well as policies and measures on decarbonisation and the energy efficiency dimensions. In particular, Spain's 2030 main targets are:

- **23% reduction in GHG emissions** compared to 1990;
- **42% of renewables** in energy end-use;
- **39.5% improvement in energy efficiency**;
- **74% share of renewable energy** in electricity generation.

Like the other national plans, this one also highlights impacts related to the social sphere, such as: employment impacts, impact on public health and on public administrations¹⁹.

¹⁹ Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan for Spain: <https://bit.ly/36VSsdL>

Wholesale and retail electricity market in Spain

Since the beginning of 1998, the **Spanish electricity sector has undergone an important transformation** as a result of the regulatory modifications carried out in our country following the approval of Directive 96/92/EC, whose main objective was to take the first steps towards the creation of an internal electricity market in the European Union based on the liberalisation of electricity generation and commercialization activities.

Law 54/1997 of 27 November 1997 on the Electricity Sector (Electricity Sector Law, LSE in Spanish) transposed the aforementioned directive into Spanish law, substantially modifying the regulatory framework in force up to that time. The basic purpose of this law, as stated in its preamble, is to establish the regulation of the electricity sector, with the **triple and traditional objective of guaranteeing the electricity supply, guaranteeing the quality of this supply, and ensuring that it is carried out at the lowest possible cost, all without forgetting environmental protection**. The regulatory principles on which the reform introduced by the LSE is based are:

- the separation between regulated activities (transmission and distribution) and those that can be carried out **under free competition (generation and commercialization)**;
- the **progressive liberalisation** of the contracting and choice of supplier for end consumers;
- **freedom of access to the transmission and distribution networks** through the payment of tolls and;
- the creation of the **system operator responsible for technical management** and the **market operator responsible for the economic management** of the system.

Subsequently, in 2003, with the approval of Directive 2003/54/EC, the European institutions gave new impetus to the process of liberalisation of the electricity sector. Law 17/2007, of 4 July, transposed the aforementioned directive into Spanish law, although it is true that a large part of these measures had already been incorporated beforehand. The most relevant modification of Law 17/2007 refers to the elimination of integral tariffs and the introduction of the activity of Last Resort.

2012 and 2013 were years with many regulatory changes in the electricity sector, while some measures sought to reduce system costs (first the premiums for the special regime with Royal Decree-Law 1/2012, then the rest of the system costs in Royal Decree-Law 13/2012, Royal Decree-Law 20/2012, Royal Decree-Law 2/2013 and Royal Decree-Law 9/2013), Law 15/2012 seeks, through fiscal measures for electricity generation activity, to raise new revenue for the system. All these initiatives sought to resolve the serious problem of the tariff deficit in the Spanish electricity system.

Royal Decree-Law 1/2012 abolishes the procedure for registration in the pre-allocation register, and therefore the economic incentives for all special regime facilities that are not registered in this register. It also suspends indefinitely the procedures for registration in the Remuneration Pre-allocation Register provided for in Royal Decree-Law 6/2009 and Royal Decree 1578/2008 (for photovoltaic solar energy installations) and renders ineffective the holding of calls for the pre-allocation of remuneration for 2012 and subsequent years.

Royal Decree-Law 13/2012 of March 2012 is also a significant regulatory package, affecting all activities in the energy chain: generation, transmission, distribution, commercialization and consumption, as well as modifying certain responsibilities and aspects related to the operation or remuneration of bodies or agents such as the National Markets and Competition Commission (CNMC in Spanish), the Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving (IDAE in Spanish) or the Electricity System Operator. It imposes new measures with the aim of reducing system costs and reducing the tariff deficit from 2013 onwards. To this end, it proposes, among other actions, the following measures:

- **reduction in remuneration for distribution and transmission**, which reopens the debate on the principle of legal certainty;
- **definition of the self-consumer** as a consumer and not as a producer, giving legal protection to the reform being processed on self-consumption;
- **reduction in the amount to be paid to electricity generation companies** for, among other things, the power guarantee.

Similarly, **measures were adopted to correct the remuneration of generation activity** in the island and non-mainland electricity systems, through the cost recognized for the acquisition of fuel and linking the payment for guaranteed power to the actual availability of the plants.

In July 2012, Royal Decree-Law 20/2012 was published, approving various measures to **guarantee budgetary stability and promote competitiveness**. The measures approved revolve around two axes: fiscal consolidation and the promotion of new structural reforms.

In addition to this measure, the following measures have been taken: **the remuneration of recurrent expenses** included in the calculation of the power guarantee **has been eliminated**; **the rate for calculating the financial remuneration of the investment** has been revised to **correspond to the value of 10-year government bonds plus 200 basis points**, instead of the previous 300 basis points; and the **unit values of the recognized fixed operation and maintenance costs have been reduced by 10%**.

The obligation to impose on access tolls and last resort tariffs a territorial supplement that will cover the totality of the additional cost caused by regional taxes and which must be paid by consumers located in the territorial scope of the respective Autonomous Community.

In December 2012, Law 15/2012 on fiscal measures for energy sustainability was approved. This law is notable for the **creation of three new taxes**: the tax on the **value of electricity production** (7%), the tax on the **production of spent nuclear fuel and radioactive waste** resulting from nuclear power generation, and the tax on the **storage of spent nuclear fuel and radioactive waste** in centralised facilities. In addition, it creates a tax on the use of inland waters to produce electricity, recently increased to 25.5% in Royal Decree-Law 10/2017; the tax rates established for natural gas and coal are modified, and the exemptions foreseen for energy products used in the production of electricity and in the cogeneration of electricity and useful heat are eliminated.

2013 also began with new urgent measures approved by the government in Royal Decree-Law 2/2013 on urgent measures in the electricity system and the financial sector, which establishes new adjustments in electricity sector costs:

- it limits the ability to choose the option of selling energy to the market, by preventing special regime facilities that opt for sale on the free market from later being able to opt for sale at the regulated tariff;
- the winning installations in the tender for innovative solar thermoelectric technology installations will maintain their remuneration set in competitive competition;
- The reference premium existing until now (as well as the upper and lower limits of the production price) is abolished and a regulated tariff is set for these installations (renewables and cogeneration);
- The updating of the remuneration of regulated activities of the electricity system linked to the Consumer Price Index (CPI) -transmission, distribution, tariffs, and premiums of the Special Regime- will now be based on the Consumer Price Index at constant taxes without unprocessed foodstuffs or energy products.

In addition, on 13 July Royal Decree-Law 9/2013 was published, adopting urgent measures to guarantee the financial stability of the electricity system, and forming part of a broad regulatory package whose main purpose is to provide financial stability to the electricity system. At the end of 2013, the new Electricity Sector Law, Law 24/2013 was published as a result of all the changes that have occurred in the sector since 1997, the impossibility of guaranteeing the financial balance of the electricity system and the recent regulatory dispersion. Law 24/2013 establishes the regulation of the electricity sector with the aim of guaranteeing the supply of electricity and adapting it to the needs in terms of safety, quality, efficiency, objectivity, transparency and at the minimum cost for consumers.

To conclude with the regulatory changes approved in 2013, Royal Decree 1047/2013 and Royal Decree 1048/2013 were published, establishing the methodology for calculating the remuneration of electricity transmission and distribution activities, respectively.

In June 2014, Royal Decree 413/2014 was published, establishing the methodology for the specific remuneration scheme, which will be applicable to production facilities using renewable energy sources, high-efficiency cogeneration, and waste to which it is granted. Subsequently, Order IET/1045/2014 was published, approving the remuneration parameters of the standard installations applicable to certain electricity production facilities using renewable energy sources, cogeneration, and waste.

In October 2015, Royal Decree 900/2015 was published, regulating the technical and economic conditions of the modalities of electricity supply with self-consumption and production with self-consumption. This Royal Decree created the Administrative Register of Self-consumption in which all installations must be registered except isolated installations, which are outside the scope of this Royal Decree.

In 2016, Royal Decree 56/2017 of 12 February was approved, transposing Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency, with regard to energy audits. The main objective to be achieved with this Royal Decree is to encourage and promote a set of actions to be carried out within the energy consumption processes that can contribute to the saving and efficiency of the primary energy consumed.

In December of the same year, Royal Decree-Law 7/2016 was approved, regulating the mechanism for financing the cost of the social bonus and other measures to protect vulnerable consumers.

In October 2015, Royal Decree 947/2017 was approved, establishing a call for the granting of the remuneration regime for new biomass electricity production facilities in the peninsular electricity system and for wind power facilities with a maximum quota of 700 MW, of which 200 MW were for biomass facilities and 500 MW for wind power technology.

Later, in March 2017, the call for the holding of the second renewable energy auction called under Royal Decree-Law 359/2017 for the allocation of 3,000 MW of installed capacity was approved. Subsequently, in April, Order ETU/315/2017 of 6 April was approved, regulating the procedure for the allocation of the specific remuneration scheme in the call for new electricity production facilities from renewable energy sources. The result of the second auction held on 17 May 2017 resulted in the award of 3,000 MW of renewable facilities, the maximum foreseen and at no cost to the consumer as the successful bidders offered the maximum possible discount. Of these 3,000 MW, 2,979 MW were awarded to wind installations, leaving only 1 MW for photovoltaic and 20 MW for other technologies, mainly biomass.

In June 2017, Royal Decree 650/2017 was approved, establishing an initial quota of 3,000 MW of installed capacity for new electricity production facilities using renewable energy sources, which was subsequently extended to 5,000 MW. The auction concluded with 3,909 MW awarded to photovoltaic and 1,128 MW for wind, closing the day with a total of 5,037 MW of renewables. Moreover, on 6 October 2017, the Government approved Royal Decree 897/2017, which regulates the figure of vulnerable consumers and other measures to protect domestic consumers. Two types of consumers are distinguished: vulnerable consumers, who receive a 25% discount and severely vulnerable consumers, who receive a 40% discount, introducing for the first time the income criterion for accessing the social voucher.

Finally, Royal Decree-Law 1/2019, was approved on 11th January, on urgent measures to adapt the powers of the National Markets and Competition Commission to the requirements derived from EU law in relation to Directives 2009/72/EC and 2009/73/EC, amends Law 24/2013, giving the National Markets and Competition Commission (CNMC in Spanish), among others, the powers to approve the methodology, remuneration parameters, the regulatory asset base and the annual remuneration of the transmission activity as well as the operation of the system.

Within the scope of these powers, the CNMC approved Circular 5/2019, of 5 December, establishing the methodology for calculating the remuneration of the electricity transmission activity, which together with Circular 2/2019, of 12 November, establishing the methodology for calculating the financial remuneration rate for electricity transmission and distribution and regasification activities, transport and distribution of natural gas, and Circular 7/2019, of 5 December, which approves the standard installations and the unit reference values for operation and maintenance per fixed asset element to be used in the calculation of the remuneration of companies owning electricity transmission facilities, establish the current regulatory remuneration framework for the electricity transmission activity in Spain.

In accordance with the aforementioned Royal Decree-Law 1/2019, the methodology for the calculation of remuneration for the operation of the electricity system is also established by the CNMC. Circular 4/2019, of 27 November, which establishes the methodology for the remuneration of the electricity system operator, establishes the methodology for the remuneration of the system operator from 2020 onwards.

Demand-response market in Spain

In regulatory terms, the **energy community does not currently have a legal identity in Spain**. There is a need for a legal order both in the civil and commercial part. Thus, **Order IET/2013/2013 and its subsequent amendments regulate the competitive mechanism for the allocation of the interruptibility demand response service** (which is the concept that comes closest in Spain to the full definition of demand response) to be carried out through an auction procedure managed by the System Operator. The regulatory framework of the mechanism consists of:

- **Order IET/2013/2013** of October 31, which regulates the competitive mechanism for the allocation of the interruptibility demand response service (and its subsequent amendments).
- **Resolution of August 1, 2014**, of the Secretary of State for Energy, approving the electricity system operation procedures 14.11 "Settlement and invoicing of the interruptibility demand response service" and 15.2 "Interruptibility demand management service".
- **Resolution of December 11, 2019**, of the Secretary of State for Energy, approving certain operating procedures for their adaptation to Royal Decree 244/2019. Includes Operating Procedure 15.2 "Interruptibility demand response service", approved by Resolution of August 1, 2014.
- **Order SND/260/2020**, of March 19, suspending the activation of the interruptibility demand response service due to economic criteria in view of the health crisis caused by COVID-19.

Regarding specifically energy communities in Spain, Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources establishes the obligation for Member States to ensure that consumers have the right to participate in a renewable energy community. It also establishes that renewable energy communities have the right to produce, consume, store, or sell renewable energy, or share within the community the renewable energy they generate and to access all energy markets. It also mandates Member States to provide a framework to encourage and facilitate the development of renewable energy communities.

As stated above, Directive (EU) 2019/944 establishes an obligation on Member States to provide a favourable legal framework for citizen energy communities. The transposition of certain aspects regarding renewable energy communities has been carried out through Royal Decree-Law 23/2020, Article 4.j. **Renewable Energy Communities** are defined as legal entities based on open and voluntary participation, autonomous and effectively controlled by partners or members that are located in the vicinity of renewable energy projects owned and developed by such legal

entities, whose partners or members are natural persons, SMEs or local authorities, including municipalities and whose primary purpose is to provide environmental, economic or social benefits to their partners or members or to the local areas where they operate, rather than financial gain.

Thus, in the area of shared consumption, the more advanced option of energy communities will allow several consumer-producers to exchange their surplus energy. In Spain, **energy communities are less deployed than in other European countries, especially due to the need for a regulatory model that contemplates them and the emergence of business models that make them viable.**

On the other hand, **the regulation of demand response in Spain** and the subsequent deployment of solutions that allow it to be carried out **will be very important factors in finding the balance between the deployment and integration of renewable energies and the electrification of the energy sector.**

This Energy Community figure is decisive for the consumer to take a step forward when it comes to regulating their consumption, taking some kind of benefit in exchange, from simply achieving savings on their electricity bill to the limit of actively participating, through a third party, in the electricity markets. Currently, the most similar reference that could be found in Spain are the interruptibility mechanisms (explained in the previous chapter) for large industrial customers, however, it is far from the concept of management or demand response.

Unlike the rest of the surrounding countries, in Spain, there is **no regulation that defines the mechanisms that allow demand aggregators to participate in the wholesale electricity market**, so there is a long way to go to position this figure as a new tool, both to respond to the needs of consumers and the energy transition.

The energy sector in Spain emphasises the **importance of addressing regulatory innovations through the sandboxes formula**, and in this sense, he referred to the recent MITECO call to finance pilot projects of energy communities and to be able to advance in the adaptation of the regulation of these figures.

Electric Vehicles (EV) and their charging stations are part of the DR market and storage mechanisms. In order to guarantee the existence of sufficient electric recharging infrastructure, Law 7/2021 introduces obligations to install electric recharging infrastructure in service stations whose annual sales of gasoline and diesel exceed 5 million litres, reaching 10% of the network. This recharging infrastructure must have a power equal to or greater than 150 kW or 50 kW depending on the volume of sales. The obligation is imposed on those service station owners who presumably have the greatest economic and financial capacity to make the required investment. In the case of concessions in state road networks, the obligations indicated will be satisfied by the concessionaires of the same. The regime of obligations will be the same as that established for the owners of facilities for the supply of fuels and combustibles to vehicles. The law includes a mandate to the Government to develop and make available to the public a platform for information on recharging points and signage.

On the other hand, it introduces the provision that the **Technical Building Code (CTE in Spanish) will establish obligations relating to the installation of electric vehicle recharging points in new**

buildings and in interventions in existing buildings (this must be completed in accordance with the low voltage technical instruction 52 (ITC-BT-52 in Spanish)), to achieve cleaner transport in cities. These regulatory measures will be accompanied by public aid to facilitate the deployment of the recharging infrastructure, in line with the Plan for the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience of the Spanish Economy, as they constitute an opportunity to take advantage of European funding and accelerate the achievement of electrification and sustainable mobility objectives with sufficient resources.

Energy efficiency in buildings in Spain

The main regulations on energy efficiency and renewable energy legislation in Spain can be grouped in the following way, trying to separate each of the sections that affect the different fields of action that the Spanish legislator has deemed appropriate. What and how are the rules on energy saving and efficiency is the purpose of this summary.

First, the energy laws in Spain have as a precedent the NBE-CT-79. (NBE CT-79 is repealed). The **Basic Building Standards (NBE in Spanish) were once fundamental for the regulatory development of buildings and facilities** in this country and were in force during the 80s and a large part of the 90s. The energy efficiency of buildings left much to be desired; **energy priorities were more focused on production than on energy savings.**

The **Building Management Law (LOE in Spanish) established minimum criteria for safety, functionality, security, and habitability.** It was the first step towards the unification, or at least its attempt, of the different regulations on the construction of a building and is not considered an energy efficiency regulation.

The **Regulation of Thermal Installations in Buildings (RITE in Spanish)** began to outline efficiency parameters in DHW and air conditioning installations, which had no regulatory support in Spanish legislation, to avoid energy wastage, it was the main energy efficiency law until very recently.

The first version of the standard dates back to 1998 (Royal Decree 1751/1998), repealed by Royal Decree 1027/2007 to be finally included in the Technical Building Code (CTE) as Section HE-2 (performance of thermal installations) within DB-HE. This section is the energy efficiency regulation for buildings.

Regulations on Energy Certifications in Buildings

The legislation on energy efficiency in Spain has undergone important modifications, being fundamental to the Royal Decree 47/2007 on Energy Certification in Buildings (More information on R.D. 47/2007). This was the first Royal Decree on energy efficiency and laid the foundations for all the laws that followed.

This Royal Decree was repealed by Royal Decree 235/2013, as it transposed the Energy Efficiency Directive and its European legislation. This law modified the regulation of energy efficiency certificates by considering the accumulated experience of the application of R.D. 47/2007 in the last five years until the new Royal Decree was approved.

This has meant an **important change that has affected the real estate market and the process of renting and selling real estate** because when building, renting, or selling a property, **an energy efficiency certificate must be shared with the buyer or tenant, whether a company or an individual.**

Thus, the owner of a building obtains an energy label with an energy rating with which he can save energy if he implements the recommendations of the certificate and its energy label.

Each Autonomous Community has a register of energy certificates that depends on the Ministry of each administration.

Energy Audits and Energy Service Providers

Royal Decree 56/2016 transposes Directive 2012/27/EU regarding energy audits and accreditation of energy service providers and auditors. It is the so-called energy companies in Spain that need its services to improve their energy efficiency.

Among other issues, this directive obliges companies of a certain size to present energy audits and regulates who can carry them out (energy service companies). An **energy audit establishes energy consumption and behaviour guidelines for companies.** It is responsible for energy efficiency in industry and is essential for Spain to be competitive in today's global market.

Energy service companies (ESCOs) pay for their services with the savings they obtain by improving energy efficiency. They are members of ANESE (Association of Energy Services).

Renewable energies application regulations

The **legislation on renewable energies in Spain is extensively developed for buildings in the DB-HE of the Technical Building Code (Código Técnico de la Edificación, CTE in Spanish).** There is no single renewable energy law; there are an increasing number of royal decrees, laws and regulations that affect this type of installation.

It should not be forgotten that each autonomous community can legislate in this respect and have more restrictive conditions regarding the installation of renewable energies. Also keep in mind that municipal ordinances may affect these facilities, we advise you to always ask in each municipality about it.

Legal development of efficiency services in Spain

This section will analyse and develop the financial and legal factors related to the development, deployment and promotion of energy efficiency services in Spain. It will also establish the basic guidelines for the relationship between the general factors and those that are specifically defined for energy communities.

General context of the legislation and specific financial system

The current context puts citizen energy communities on the map, since they cover a large part of the aspects analysed, such as the buildings themselves, which include not only residential sectors but also tertiary sectors of great interest, such as public facilities (hospitals, sports centers, etc.).

To this end, Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency, amending Directives 2009/125/EC and 2010/30/EU, and repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC, created a common framework to promote energy efficiency within the European Union and establishes concrete actions to implement some of the proposals included in the Energy Efficiency Plan 2011, and thus, to achieve the considerable unrealized potential for energy savings. All this is reflected in Royal Decree RD-56/2016 (related on energy efficiency, in terms of energy audits, accreditation of energy service providers and auditors, and promotion of energy supply efficiency) within the Spanish framework.

The purpose of this Royal Decree will be to boost and promote a set of actions to be carried out within the energy consumption processes that can contribute to the saving and efficiency of the primary energy consumed, as well as to optimize the energy demand of the installation, equipment or energy consuming systems, in addition to having a sufficient number of competent and reliable professionals in order to ensure the effective and timely implementation of the aforementioned Directive 2012/27/EU. In this sense, it is also about deepening the development of the energy services market in order to ensure the availability of both the demand and the supply of such services. This aspect includes, therefore, all the systems of the energy communities (at least until specific legislation appears). It also regulates in a general way the main relevant economic aspects to be taken into account within the energy services mentioned in the European Directive 2012/27/EU. This royal decree will also have a strong impact on energy auditing services, and accreditations for energy service providers, it will in turn affect approaches to the promotion of energy efficiency services as well as the efficiency of heating and cooling systems.

Energy audits with respect to energy efficiency services

Royal Decree RD 56/2016, as noted in the previous section, imposes that, in relation to energy audits, large companies or groups of companies must undergo an energy audit every four years from the date of the previous energy audit, covering at least 85 percent of their total final energy consumption. Those audits are mandatory for all the facilities located in the national territory (industrial, commercial and service activities) that such companies and groups manage in the development of their economic activity. After the entry into force of this Royal Decree, those companies that, for at least two consecutive fiscal years, comply with the condition of large company, must undergo their first energy audit within nine months, provided that they have not previously carried out one within a period of less than four years.

As can be seen, the elements of energy audits apply in the cases of production and operation elements. Within the specific KERs of the NEON project, several integrating services have been identified in the field of energy efficiency of energy communities. Thus, in Spain, companies or groups of companies are legislatively required to implement an energy or environmental management system, certified by an independent body in accordance with the relevant European or international standards, provided that the management system in question includes an energy audit carried out in accordance with the minimum guidelines (section 3 of the Royal Decree).

Thus, the services defined in NEON represent a suitable legislative applicability from the point of view of energy efficiency certification.

These actions shall also be based on updated, measured and verifiable operational data on energy consumption and, in the case of electricity, on load profiles where available. In addition, they shall cover a detailed examination of the energy consumption profile of buildings or groups of buildings, of an industrial or commercial facility or operation, or of a private or public utility, including transport within the facility or, where appropriate, vehicle fleets. These legal foundations are intrinsically linked to NEON's services as they offer measurement and verification elements, as well as significantly more accurate load estimation than conventional static mechanisms.

Likewise, Spanish legislation specifies that these premises shall be based, whenever possible, on cost-effectiveness criteria in life-cycle cost analysis, rather than on simple amortization periods, in order to take into account long-term savings, residual values of long-term investments and discount rates. Thus, such estimates should be proportionate and sufficiently representative so that a reliable picture of overall energy performance can be drawn, and the most significant improvement opportunities can be reliably identified. All of this is aligned with NEON's energy efficiency services as it maximizes efficiency while minimizing overall cost and maintaining comfort constraints.

The energy efficiency studies, in turn, will reflect detailed and validated calculations for the proposed measures, thus providing clear information on the savings potential. Thus, the data used should be able to be stored for historical analysis and traceability of energy performance. This aspect is fully validated by the features of NEON and its solution platform in a centralized and accessible way (always according to the conditions imposed in D7.3 Data Management Plan and in document D6.7 in its IPR conditions).

Last but not least, the energy studies and services shall not contain clauses preventing the transmission of the conclusions of the studies to qualified or accredited energy service providers, provided that the customer does not object, and in any case, respecting the confidentiality of the information. This aspect is really important as it will not only allow the integration of the NEON solution through the ESCOs but will also professionalize and systematize the evolution of the citizen energy communities.

Energy efficiency in the production and use of heat and cold

Spanish legislation specifically addresses energy efficiency in the case of heat and cold according to the law RD 56/2016. Thus, every five years the Ministry of Industry, Energy and Tourism will carry out and notify to the European Commission, a full assessment of the potential for the use of high efficiency cogeneration and efficient district heating and cooling systems.

This assessment shall take full account of the analyses of national potentials for high-efficiency cogeneration carried out under Directive 2004/8/EC on the promotion of cogeneration based on a useful heat demand in the internal energy market and amending Directive 92/42/EEC.

The autonomous communities and local entities may adopt policies that encourage the analysis at local and regional level of the potential for the use of efficient heating and cooling systems, in particular those using high-efficiency cogeneration. The possibilities of promoting local and regional heat markets will be taken into account. This is a relevant aspect for NEON as it will allow full adaptability to the specific needs of each region and a systematic deployment of the NEON solution (KER 19) in the Spanish territory.

In any case, policies to promote energy efficiency in the production and use of heat and cold shall at all times respect the provisions of Article 14.1 of Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector, and Article 59.2 Law 18/2014 on the approval of urgent measures for growth, competitiveness and efficiency. This aspect significantly favours the NEON solution since the aforementioned guidelines in conjunction with the current complementary ones encourage (interpretively since there is still no specific regulation) the integration of heating and cooling energy services in NEON.

Likewise, for the purposes of the cost-benefit assessment covering the Spanish territory, taking into account climatic conditions, economic feasibility and technical suitability, it should allow the determination of the most efficient solutions in relation to resources and the most cost-effective in relation to costs, to meet heating and cooling needs. NEON's technical KERs such as KER3 facilitate in a technically robust way the resolution of the combination between economic performance and the need for energy optimization (refer to D6.4).

In cases where the assessment foreseen by the above analysis identifies potential for the application of high-efficiency cogeneration of efficient district heating and/or cooling, the benefits of which outweigh its cost, appropriate measures will be taken to ensure that an efficient district heating and cooling infrastructure is developed and/or to enable the development of high-efficiency cogeneration and the use of heating and cooling from waste heat and renewable energy sources.

Otherwise, including the administrative costs of carrying out the cost-benefit analysis referred to in the following section or in article 121 bis of Royal Decree 1955/2000, which regulates the activities of transport, distribution, commercialization, supply and authorization procedures for electric energy facilities, as applicable, the Directorate General of Energy Policy and Mines may exempt the facilities from carrying out such cost-benefit analysis.

In relation to the analysis of costs and benefits of the facilities, the Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving (IDAE) will publish a methodological guide on the performance of such analysis. Where appropriate, the aforementioned cost and benefit analyses will be carried out in collaboration with the companies responsible for the operation of the district heating and cooling networks. This aspect will be applied to facilities included in the scope of application of Law 16/2002, on integrated pollution prevention and control, as well as in that of Royal Decree 815/2013 approving the regulation on industrial emissions and development of Law 16/2002 on integrated pollution prevention and control.

Accreditation for energy service providers

It has been observed that the Spanish legislation specifically allows the actions of integration of energy services (the legislative interpretation also allows it in the case of the CECs). However, it is also important to define the legislative conditions imposed to be able to act in the field of energy services according to RD56/2016.

In order to exercise the professional activity of energy service providers, the following requirements must be met, and documentation must be available to prove it:

- To have the documentation that identifies the provider, which in the case of being a legal entity, must be legally constituted and include in its corporate purpose the activities of the provision of energy services or improvement of energy efficiency in the facilities or premises of a user, and in the case of being an individual to be registered in the Census of Entrepreneurs, Professionals and Withholders in any of the groups of the Rates of the Economic Activities Tax corresponding to the economic activities of provision of energy services.
- To prove an adequate technical qualification
 - In the case of an individual, this qualification must meet one of the following conditions. In the first place, to be in possession of a university degree, other university degrees, or Masters in which knowledge in energy matters is taught. In the second place, to have theoretical and practical knowledge about energy, understanding that the persons who accredit any of the following situations have such knowledge:
 - vocational training degree or a certificate of professionalism included in the National Catalogue of Professional Qualifications whose scope of competence includes matters related to energy.
 - professional competence acquired through work experience, in accordance with the provisions of Royal Decree 1224/2009 on the recognition of professional competences acquired through work experience, in the field of energy.
 - In the case of a legal entity, the qualification will be recognised when at least one of the owners of the company meets any of the conditions described above or the company has at least one person among the employees who meets any of them, who will be responsible, with his/her signature, for all documents of a technical nature to be issued by the company.
- To be able to count on the appropriate technical means to provide the energy services in the area of activity in which the company acts, at the time of the specific action.
- To be registered in the corresponding Social Security regime, or corresponding professional, and up to date in the fulfilment of the obligations before the Social Security, for which the owner may authorize the competent body to collect the information related to the fulfilment of the obligations before the Social Security.
- In the event that they are not citizens of a Member State of the European Union or of a State party to the Agreement on the European Economic Area, and reside in Spain, they

must comply with the provisions established in the Spanish regulations in force regarding foreigners and immigration.

- Have subscribed civil liability insurance or other financial guarantee covering the risks that may arise from their actions, for a minimum amount of 150,000 euros, in accordance with Article 76 of Law 18/2014, approving urgent measures for growth, competitiveness and efficiency.
- In the case of companies that provide services that include installation and/or maintenance work, comply with the requirements established for installation and/or maintenance companies in the Regulation of Thermal Installations in Buildings (RITE), approved by Royal Decree 1027/2007. When the energy services are provided by a Temporary Joint Venture (UTE), it will be sufficient that among its members the requirements established in the aforementioned Regulation are met.

Actual and potential financing schemes

Over the past years, the commitment of governments, companies, and financial institutions to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050 encouraged the financial community to take the path towards sustainable finance; the financial community has rallied launching funds and initiatives to channel growing appetite from capital markets and to comply with new disclosure rules.

Energy-related investments often come with high transaction costs because projects are small and not sufficiently aggregated to appeal to investors. For example, energy efficiency investments such as deep retrofits of buildings tend to have relatively long paybacks, and investors are wary that the savings achieved will not justify the cost of the energy retrofit.

A further barrier to financing these projects is a certain degree of **difficulty in assessing the investment risk** that private investors may face. However, there is growing evidence that the risks associated with energy efficiency investments are lower than the level perceived by markets. The challenge is to reassure investors that energy efficiency projects are overall a safe business case and help banks and other financial organisations understand and easily assess all risks and opportunities associated with a particular project. For example, in 2018 the Board of the European Investment Bank (EIB) approved the creation of a brand-new financial instrument, the Smart Finance for Smart Buildings initiative to help to de-risk investments in the buildings sector, giving investors and financiers a better understanding of the risks and benefits of energy efficiency investments. Moreover, it will offer assistance with project development, as many households lack the skills and capacity to set up, implement and finance ambitious energy efficiency projects.

There is also an acute **need for technical and legal standardisation at all steps of the investment value chain to simplify transactions and increase the confidence of financial institutions.** The lack of standardisation of projects prevents securitisation of energy efficiency assets (loans or equity) so that financial institutions are not able to refinance their debt on the capital markets.

From a consumer point of view, the cost of energy efficiency investments is expected to be recouped exclusively through the reduction in energy bills, but there is growing evidence that **non-energy benefits play a key role in the decision to invest in energy efficiency.** These include better comfort and indoor health parameters, increased building value, lower probability of mortgage default, and lower tenant turnover or vacancy rates. Thus, there are tangible financial and economic carrots to entice financial institutions to invest more in energy efficiency.

The implementation of energy-related projects can be supported through private or public funds. Private funds include financial instruments from commercial banks, investment funds and crowdfunding platforms. Public sources include European institutions' funds, national and regional funds, National and International Development Banks, etc. Both kinds of funding bodies are interested, for different reasons, in supporting the energy transition process, with the aim on the public side to reach carbon-neutrality objectives set at EU level for 2030 and 2050 and, on the private side, to meet mandatory and voluntary targets for sustainable investments and minimum financial performances to generate revenues for investors.

The role of sustainable finance

More financial innovation and a broadening of the range of actors and beneficiaries of sustainable finance are necessary for the achievement of the 2050 climate target. These elements reduce the risk associated with energy efficiency investments, which can be supported by the development and use of digital platforms. De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform (DEEP), for example, is an open-source initiative to expand energy efficiency investments in Europe through better sharing and transparent analysis of existing projects in buildings and industry²⁰.

Public funding opportunities

Public investments in the energy transition are very important to reach national and EU level targets for energy efficiency, penetration of renewables and mitigating climate change. They may act directly to support the implementation of projects or indirectly to stimulate and mobilise private investments in specific areas like strategic infrastructures, enabling technologies, early-stage projects or solutions perceived as high risk by private investors.

EU funding programs

Because of energy systems' innovation's relevance for EU climate objectives, European institutions are fully committed to financing dedicated projects such as NEON. EU funding programmes will ensure **direct co-financing of investments** in energy efficiency and **leverage private and public investments** through tailored financial instruments and project development assistance. These programmes also support **research, innovation, and technology development**, as well as building capacity of private and public entities and addressing non-technological barriers.

The **European Commission's multi-annual financial framework 2021-2027** and **Next Generation EU** will directly co-finance energy efficiency investments in the EU through 3 different funds:

- **Recovery and Resilience Facility:** this facility will be the main source of public funding for energy efficiency in the next years, with a focus on public buildings and residential buildings, including social housing. From the total €672.5 billion, 37% should be dedicated to climate action. Based on the Recovery and Resilience Plans, submitted by EU countries, energy efficiency and building renovation are very important components in almost all plans.
- **Cohesion policy funds:** these include the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund Plus, the Cohesion Fund, the Just Transition Fund and INTERREG. The total budget of €373 billion will be an important funding source for direct investments into energy efficiency.
- **Modernisation Fund:** the fund was established under the Emissions Trading Scheme Directive with a volume of about €14 billion and made available to 10 lower-income EU countries to support investments in the modernisation of their energy systems and energy efficiency improvements.

²⁰ De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform. For more information: <https://bit.ly/3CanslQ>

European institutions are also committed to mobilising investments by stimulating public-private partnerships. The main actual **funding programmes for energy services** are:

- **InvestEU**: aims to mobilise public and private financing in the form of loans, guarantees, equity or other market-based instruments for strategic investments in the support of EU internal policies. It is divided into 4 policy windows; sustainable infrastructure (€ 9.9 billion); research, innovation, and digitisation (€ 6.6 billion); SMEs (€ 6.9 billion); social investment and skills (€ 2.8 billion). InvestEU acts as a single investment support mechanism with an EU guarantee of €26.2 billion with the objective to leverage €370 billion. Energy efficiency will be supported under all 4 windows, but mainly under sustainable infrastructure.
- **Horizon Europe**: supports research and innovation projects in technology development to increase the efficiency of energy use. Its “cluster 5” is specifically dedicated to climate, energy and mobility and includes an area focusing on energy efficiency in buildings and industry and on the sustainable built environment, with dedicated funding of €244 million of funding for the first 2 years of the work programme. It was preceded by Horizon 2020, the biggest EU Research and Innovation programme ever with nearly €80 billion of funding available over 7 years (2014 to 2020).
- **Innovation Fund**: is one of the world’s largest funding programmes for the demonstration of innovative low-carbon technologies in the areas of energy-intensive industry, renewable energy, energy storage and carbon capture and storage (CCS). The fund supports innovation that can bring on significant emission reductions, for instance by replacing high energy-intensive processes and technologies with more energy-efficient alternatives.
- **LIFE-Clean Energy Transition sub-programme**: has a total budget envelope of €1 billion and will support energy efficiency by addressing structural or organisation obstacles, setting the favourable enabling framework and building capacity of public and private actors. It will continue successful funding initiatives removing market barriers and developing EU-wide best practices for energy efficiency policy implementation. It is a continuation of H2020 energy efficiency market funding previously also supported under the (archived) Intelligent Energy Europe programme.

Other initiatives are:

- The **European Energy Efficiency Fund (EEEF)**: is an innovative public-private partnership dedicated to mitigating climate change through energy efficiency measures and the use of renewable energy in the Member States of EU. It aims to enable projects in European cities, regions and communities to build resilient infrastructure.²¹
- **Private Finance for Energy Efficiency (PF4EE)**: is a joint agreement between the European Investment Bank and the EC aiming at addressing the limited access to suitable and affordable private financing for energy efficiency investments. It should help the MS implement their National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAPs) or other programmes in

²¹ EEEF – European Energy Efficiency Fund. For more information: <https://bit.ly/3pDA6Vn>

line with EU Directives related to energy efficiency. Its two main objectives are: to enhance energy efficiency lending within European financial institutions; to increase the availability of debt financing for energy efficiency investments. PF4EE is managed by the EIB and funded by the Programme for the Environment and Climate Action (LIFE programme, DG Clima). The instrument provides three types of support: 1. A portfolio-based credit risk protection (Risk Sharing Facility); 2. Long-term financing from the EIB (EIB Loan for Energy Efficiency); 3. Expert support for financial intermediaries (Expert Support Facility).

- **Green Economy Financing Facility (GEFF):** spearheaded by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), it supports businesses and homeowners wishing to invest in green technologies. The GEFF programme operates through a network of more than 140 local financial institutions across 26 countries supported by more than EUR 4 billion of EBRD finance. This has enabled more than 130,000 clients to collectively avoid almost 7 million tonnes of CO2 emissions per year. GEFF goes beyond providing simple lines of finance. An experienced EBRD team of bankers and technical programme managers ensures consistent quality and innovation in the GEFF product and service delivery. In addition, advisory services are available to help participating financial institutions and their clients enhance their market practices.

Setting favourable framework conditions is necessary to ensure private financing supply to investments in energy efficiency of buildings, industry, transport, and other sectors. This process takes place in the broader context of the **EU policy focus on Sustainable Finance** and the development of the new Strategy for Financing the Transition to a Sustainable Economy (adopted by European Commission in July 2021), which also covers the financing framework for energy efficiency investments.

FIG.24 - European Funding programme

Source: Image processed by SIF

Other public funding opportunities

The European funds need to be complemented by further national financing mechanisms. Well-designed national and local funds can be a key driver of energy efficiency investments. EU Member States typically allocate national funds to invest directly in projects related to public assets (public buildings, energy infrastructures, public transport systems, etc.) or to attract private investments through incentives and grants (e.g., for buildings retrofitting, for energy efficiency interventions, for renewable energy production, etc.). The mentioned national funds may, on one hand, rely on funds allocated from the EU budget or, on the other hand, be channelled through regions or other local authorities.

Among funding sources promoted by national and local authorities, **Public-Private Partnerships (PPP)** and **public incentives** to support private investments in the energy field are particularly relevant. Public-Private Partnership is defined as a long-term contract between a private party and a government agency for providing a public asset or service, in which the private party bears significant risk and management responsibility (World Bank, 2012). It relies on the recognition that public and private sectors each have certain advantages relative to others in performing specific tasks. An example is the Energy Efficient Buildings (EEB) PPP, which promotes and supports research and innovation to reduce energy consumption and CO₂ emissions for new and retrofitted buildings across Europe. The EeB PPP is a partnership between the European Commission which stands for public interest and the E2B Committee of ECTP representing the private sector. The PPP is not just a financing instrument, but also a mechanism of dialogue between industry and the European Commission.²²

In terms of public incentives, they are usually implemented in different ways in the EU Member States. For instance, mechanisms rewarding the operation rather than the realisation of projects are feed-in tariffs for renewable energy projects, which are paid by national regulatory authorities per unit of electricity produced, or white certificates for energy efficiency projects, which are issued per unit of saved primary energy. Another mechanism supporting the realisation of investments is based on tax deduction, which allows subtracting from taxes part of the expenses borne for energy efficiency or renewable energy projects. This is applicable both to individuals and legal persons and is of particular interest in Member States with high tax rates. The tax deduction can typically be recovered over a time-span of 5-10 years but in some cases, it is also possible to transfer the tax credit to a bank or even to the contractor that realises the works. A relevant initiative of tax deduction for energy efficiency investments in Italy is the so-called “Superbonus”, a financial incentive introduced through the “Decreto Rilancio” (Law decree 19th May 2020, n.34) in 2020 which offers a deduction rate that's been increased to 110% on expenses for energy measures on residential buildings. The introduction of this instrument has had a relevant impact on the market. First, it increased citizens’ interests and awareness on the issue of energy efficiency and home renovation. After the announcement of the policy, the market reacted both from the demand and the supply sides of renovation services. From the demand side, homeowners and condominiums were the main target recipients of the policy, while from the supply side the banks have by now steadily adapted their operations to suit the new needs of the market: new products have been developed, allowing a variety of final beneficiaries to obtain

²² Energy Efficient Buildings. For more information: <https://bit.ly/34bePuG>

the necessary funding for accessing the renovation works. The possibility to trade the fiscal credit (e.g., credit assignment) has brought new solutions also for natural people willing to trade their credits. The institution of **credit exchange platforms** allows the final user (belonging to one of the categories eligible for accessing the bonus, meaning that this solution is not allowed strictly for natural people) to buy or sell a fiscal credit according to financial needs. The person selling the credit aims at receiving the discounted financial amount in advance, for liquidity purposes, while the party selling the credit can purchase a tax credit to close any open position towards the fiscal agency while profiting off the value differential. A recent example of such a platform is SiBonus, developed by InfoCamere, the association of the Italian Chamber of Commerce promoting digitalization, with the support of Sinloc. The platform shows the user what are the available credits (which have previously undergone the verification process), which is the fiscal bonus and the intervention that created it, as well as the prize and the geographical location. The platform allows to trade of any kind of tax credit deriving from renovation activities. Similar services are provided by the “Piattaforma Cessione del Credito”, managed directly by the Italian fiscal agency, and by Cribis, developed by Crif and Workinvoice (PadovaFIT Expanded 2022).

FIG. 25 - Investment volume activated by the Superbonus for condominiums (blue line), single-family buildings (orange line) and independent units (grey line)

Source: ENEA, 2021: <https://bit.ly/3MU5fhB>

PRIVATE FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES

The possibilities of having access to private financing opportunities for energy innovation interventions are ever more numerous.

The most common financial product from the private sector is constituted by **loans**; they are applicable to projects of any scale and to any client, depending on the financial solvency evaluation of the borrower or on the financial performance of the project to be realised. Funds provided by banks through loans can typically cover only part of the investment, with an equity component to be provided by the project promoter through equity or other sources of funding

including public grants. Specific credit lines or financial products may exist for supporting energy-related investments, but these are generally related either to the presence of public incentives (e.g., transfer of tax credit) or to the support of an international financial institution (e.g., the EIB's Private Finance for Energy Efficiency (PF4EE) facility and the EBRD with the Green Economy Financing Facility (GEFF), implemented through local commercial banks).

Soft loans are loans with no interest or below-market rate of interest. They may also have lenient terms, such as extended grace periods, in which only interest or service charges are due, or interest holidays. Soft loans are often used by states, regions, or local authorities to encourage investment supporting energy policies. They are often complementary to subsidies of fiscal incentives. Soft loans are particularly suitable for citizens wishing to carry out energy renovation works in their homes, a pole that represents around 35% of a city's total energy consumption, and therefore a great potential for energy savings (Compete4SECAP 2021).

Innovative financing schemes related to energy efficiency have also developed in the mortgage sector. **Energy Efficient Mortgages (EEMs)** encourage energy efficiency by giving buyers a better rate or more borrowing capacity to buy an energy-efficient house or to cover the cost of new energy improvements. For an EEM program, state and local governments typically engage via credit enhancement, such as an interest rate buy-down or loan loss reserve.

EEMs give property owners the opportunity to finance cost-effective, energy-saving measures as part of a single mortgage. The mortgage can allow a repayment period between 15 to 30 years, thus amortising the costs of the energy efficiency improvement over time. Property owners can secure an EEM at the time that they purchase a home or refinance their existing mortgage.

The mortgage industry is an essential player in efforts to tackle climate change through its funding of the home renovation programmes needed to improve the energy performance of the EU's building stock. Therefore, the European institutions promote this type of instrument: since its inception in 2015, the EU Horizon 2020 funded the Energy Efficient Mortgages Initiative (EEMI) for the growth of a new, integrated, multi-stakeholder energy efficient mortgage ecosystem²³.

Another potential source of private finance is constituted by **investment funds**, whose aim is to invest funds collected from individuals and corporate investors into medium/long-term risk capital of companies with high expected growth potential, to generate revenues for investors. The time horizon of projects supported by investment funds is, at least, five years and may be longer for patient capital like those from pension funds. The exponential growth of sustainable and responsible investments in recent years has led to the proliferation of sustainable investment funds, including those dedicated to energy efficiency, renewable energy, and the transition to clean energy in general. Research carried out in 2021 by the Italian SIF on the integration of sustainability criteria in the main Italian pension schemes shows that almost half of the plans active in sustainable investments adopt the strategy of impact investing; this kind of investments focus mostly on environmental aspects and on renewable energy and green bonds (FFS 2021).

On-bill financing and **on-bill repayment programs** provide two options for property owners to pay for investments in clean energy upgrades through their utility. While electric utilities and

²³ Energy Efficient Mortgages Initiative. For more information: <https://bit.ly/3CdPNrl>

natural gas companies typically run on-bill programs, there is an opportunity for state and local governments to capitalise on new on-bill loan funds and/or provide credit enhancement for existing on-bill funds. Depending on the programs available in each jurisdiction, some government entities may also be able to take advantage of on-bill programs to finance projects for their own facilities. On-bill financing allows the utility to incur the cost of the clean energy upgrade, which is then repaid on the utility bill. On-bill repayment options require the customer to repay the investment through a charge on their monthly utility bill as well, but with this option, the upfront capital is provided by a third party, not the utility. Additionally, on-bill repayment allows for a streamlined process as utilities already have a billing relationship with their customers, as well as access to information about their energy usage patterns and payment history. In some on-bill repayment programs, the loan is transferable to the next owner of the home or building.

One of the most interesting financial schemes within the NEON project is that of **Energy Performance Contracting (EPC)**. EPC is a form of **innovative financing of energy efficiency investments, where the contractor gives a financial guarantee for the expected energy savings on a project**. An energy service company carries out the work and guarantees a certain level of energy savings. The initial investment is covered by the energy service company or by a private partner (usually a financial institution) and repaid through the guaranteed energy savings. An EPC is a particular form of contract because **remuneration is closely linked to the success of the interventions** carried out by the supplier that can focus on both the energy saving of the project and on the use of renewable energy.

There are two main actors in executing EPC contracts: the beneficiary of the energy efficiency improvement measures and the supplier of those energy efficiency measures. The beneficiary can be the owner or the tenant of the infrastructure, i.e., the one paying the energy costs. The supplier normally is a certain kind of company called Energy Service Company (ESCO): its function, in addition to implementing the energy savings measures, is to anticipate or pre-finance the costs of the energy efficiency intervention or to assume the burden to find the capital. The EPC approach is based on the transfer of technical and performance risks from the client (beneficiary) to the ESCo (supplier) based on performance guarantees given by the ESCO. As said before, in EPCs, ESCo remuneration is based on demonstrated performance; a measure of performance is the level of energy savings or energy service. A third contractual party sometimes present in a EPC agreement is the financier which is not intended in the classic way of a financial institution that provides a loan covered by solid guarantees to the beneficiary or the ESCo, but instead, as a subject which participates in the investment by providing debt or equity, whose return is linked to the achievement of the contractual targets (project cash flows), also known as project finance: for this reason, it takes the operation risks on himself. A fourth possible actor is the "facilitator" who has the aim of providing strategic, technical, administrative and financing assistance in the field of energy efficiency investments to a possible customer to guide the latter through its EPC project. This figure is particularly active with the public administration (Ambience 2020).

EPC is a promising financing and services model, strongly supported by European energy efficiency policy and legislation. Several provisions of the Energy Efficiency Directive have a direct or indirect impact on the market uptake of the energy performance contracts (EPCs). The

provisions on energy services directly contribute to EPCs services development, while the provisions on the exemplary role of the public sector, as well as the provisions establishing energy savings obligations have an indirect triggering effect on the demand for EPCs.

FIG.26 - Third Party Financing with ESCO borrowing and TPF with energy-user/customer borrowing: summary of relations

Source: ECS 2003: <https://bit.ly/3t3QG32>

One of the potentially most interesting private funding schemes for energy-related projects such as NEON is **crowdfunding**. Crowdfunding is a funding scheme that relies on capital collected from many private investors (both individuals and corporates) through an online crowdfunding platform. In case of “equity crowdfunding”, investors are rewarded with the dividends generated by the supported company (or project) whereas in case of “loan crowdfunding”, investors are rewarded with their capital plus the agreed interest rate. This solution is particularly of interest for projects to be realised at a small and medium scale, like in the case of the creation of energy communities, i.e., a group of citizens and small businesses acting jointly to self-produce energy from renewables. Crowdfunding schemes allow the final user to access an alternative form of funds with respect to the usual banking credit, reducing the intermediation costs through the involvement of a community of smaller investors interested in obtaining financial gains.

The structure of the “loan crowdfunding”, also known as Peer-to-Peer lending, has some elements in common with the typical loan structure: after having reached the capital requested, the reimbursement plan foresees the payment of a core capital component and an interest component, at rates which are usually higher than those applied by the financial institutions. “Equity-based” schemes on the other hand are based on a structure that is more similar to a direct investment, where the lender becomes the substantial owner of a determined share of the entity, or the project financed. Due to the ownership and administrative rights that are associated with

the shareholder status, more rigid controls are generally performed to prevent fraudulent behaviours.

Crowdfunding schemes are becoming a **feasible alternative to classic loans and mortgages in financing energy-related projects**. Aside from “general” platforms, which raise investments without being sector-specific, it is possible to notice a constant growth in the availability of platforms with a sole focus on energy efficiency and energy transition projects. Energy crowdfunding platforms are becoming popular to finance the energy transition of the European countries, especially in Great Britain, France, Netherlands and Germany and a certain degree of interest towards these new solutions has been shown by banking operators as well: institutions such as Banca Etica or Credit Agricole are exploiting crowdfunding schemes as a powerful tool for promoting post-pandemic recovery and development at the local level.

To deepen into the financial framework for each energy services that NEON pilots already implement or will implement in the future, the table below includes an analysis and estimation of the payback period of each energy service, possible financial instruments and channels to implement the services, and a brief analysis of drivers and obstacles to financing each specific service.

Energy Service	Payback Period	Financial Channels	Drivers	Barriers
Collective self-consumption	Mid-long term	credit institutions, retail energy company, financial investors of the energy sector, grants and subsidies, own financing (private capital)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilities' prices reduction - Network connection rates reduction - Public grants and incentives - Electricity price rise - Electricity price rise - Reduction of maintenance costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High capital costs - Price of PV modules - Cost of batteries - Financing difficulties - Investment rate of return - Initial investment - Low cost-effectiveness - Uncertain returns in the short term
Energy electricity compensation with hydrogen storage during the off PV production period	Long term	banking disintermediation through the financing of the retail energy company, cost savings in equipment, in addition to the financing provided by public subsidies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexible contracts for consumers - Reduction of pollutants in the environment (clean energy and long lifetime) - Revenue generation - Utility scale storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legislative and administrative barriers at the national level - High price - Techno-environmental barriers (such us: natural topography, land use, vegetation clearing) - Cost overruns - Resettlement issues

HVAC system optimization and control	Short-mid term	Banking loans, crowdfunding, own financing, EPC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovation, R&D - High impact on final energy consumption - Supporting automatic DR mechanisms - Public incentives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital divide - Contractors' trustworthiness and expertise - Market reliant on public subsidies - HVAC possible lack of experience/interest on EE - Awareness and education of building owners
EV charging from clean resources	Short- Mid term	Public subsidies or private energy companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Profit of public charging infrastructures - Charging demand - Charging price - Electricity price in comparison to fuel price 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Installation costs can reduce profitability - Unit subsidy for construction - Unit subsidy for operation - Ground rental cost - Maintenance cost - Number of charging unit to provide

Actual and potential barriers for NEON

There are numerous barriers faced by various stakeholders which need to be considered in the process of depicting and implementing financial and non-financial support mechanisms for energy services in energy communities (Ruggeri 2021).

Barriers could be from consumers' perspective, from market actors' or from policy actors' point of view.

One of the main issues that can negatively affect the individual consumer (potential prosumer) is the problem of **split incentives**. It refers to any situation where the benefits of a transaction do not accrue to the actor who pays for the transaction. For example, in the context of energy efficiency in buildings, split incentives are linked with cost recovery issues related to energy efficiency upgrade investments due to the failure of distributing effective financial obligations and rewards of these investments between concerned actors. This can ultimately result in inaction from either actor's side, even though many of these upgrades are of positive net present values. Investment costs of energy efficiency upgrades are part of the capital expenses, while its financial benefits, in the simplest form, are seen as reduced energy bills on the operational expenses side. If the actor who invests in energy efficiency measures, for example, the building owner, is not the same as the actor who reaps the subsequent financial benefits, as the tenant of the building is, split incentives can arise. Usage-related split incentives are also a good example of this kind of barrier: they occur when occupants are not responsible for paying their utility bills and thereby have little or no interest to conserve energy (Petrov, Ryan 2021).

Other potential barriers could be caused by:

- lack of knowledge about existing financial supporting schemes;
- lack of capacity to undertake the bureaucratic work associated with traditional financial supporting schemes;
- high initial costs for structural measures and lack of capacity to follow up the investment and initiate take-up of energy efficiency or renewable energy measures;
- debt aversion: even if they qualify to take a loan, low-income households tend to be reluctant to do so
- long payback times; investors are wary that the savings achieved will not justify the cost of the energy retrofit.
- lack of awareness of the multiple benefits of energy renovation and renewable energies;
- lack of confidence and trust in actual energy and economic savings associated with investments for this kind of measures; fear of incapacity of repayment, which could result in disconnection from the community. It could be a problem of risk perception.

Some possible obstacles are also to be found in the perceptions and in a more emotional and personal sphere of the consumer, for example:

- unwillingness to admit difficulties;
- lack of a “culture of saving”; lack of awareness on savings potential;
- Mistrust/negative perception of new technologies

Other barriers are from market actors’ perspective. The **lack of economic return** in implementing financial supporting schemes for the uptaking of energy efficiency or renewable energy solutions could affect the decision. At the same time, the poor spread of specific financial products/services adapted to both energy efficiency and “energy poverty” (for example soft loans, on bill payment, on tax payment) and the lack of guarantees for debt repayment can keep market players from tackling certain operations.

Other issues are:

- residential sector perceived as less profitable than others (e.g., industry) and more complicated (e.g. because of high segregation);
- risk assessment by financial entities does not consider energy efficiency/renewable energy particularities that imply the production of savings, which could be considered a sort of guarantee of repayment;
- high transaction costs;
- management of uncertainty: at present, little data on this kind of measures in the residential sector are available and open for financial institutions to use in assessing the economic viability of investments;
- lack of expertise (skills & training) and highly qualified specialists.

From policy actors’ perspective, barriers could be caused by:

- lack of knowledge on needs of energy poverty consumers and on how to address/engage/support them (lack of communication flow and proper dialogue);
- lack of capacity to set up financial schemes (lack of knowledge and capacity on funding schemes);
- poor policy for energy efficiency/renewable energy investments (tax incentives, facilitation of administrative permits, lack of standardisation);
- low flexibility for implementing some measures; administrative and policy barriers.

Some barriers to the development of integrated energy services in energy communities, and to the organisation of CECs themselves, may be constituted by more technical issues. The availability of **cheap domestic central energy sources** can influence this kind of investments; the fossil fuel dependence for a certain geographical area can be a strong incentive for the creation of energy communities based on the implementation of renewable energy sources, but if an area has easy access to cheap energy sources it could be a barrier. A related aspect is also the individual ownership of renewable energy production systems such as photovoltaic panels: in a country like

Italy where many individuals own photovoltaic panels, the creation of energy communities and a consequent implementation of integrated energy services is harder to appreciate.

Another problem is the fact that once the CECs are structured, some issues may arise in finding a **technical and legal agreement with network operators**, in order to integrate the Communities in the system; there could be no incentives for Distribution System Operators to connect small operators to the grid, microgrids, and facilitating a “people-to-people” market. The electricity grid is a natural monopoly heavily regulated, but it can be more or less dominated by a few actors. High grid connection costs could be a strong barrier: for this reason, smart metres (net-metering and virtual net-metering systems) have been identified as an important enabler which among others makes it possible to share electricity. At last, the **lack of standardisation** of contracts underlying both funding and implementation of energy communities and their services constitutes an actual and potential obstacle to the development of this type of initiatives.

Conclusion

This report presents the **European regulatory framework** (e.g., the EU Green Deal, the Clean Energy for all Europeans Package, Electricity Market Directives, Renewable Energy Source (RES) Directive, Building Efficiency Directive) as well as **national regulations affecting NEON**. Starting from an analysis of the **functioning of the electricity markets in Europe**, the deliverable proceeds with **specific focuses on self-consumption, demand-response, and energy efficiency in buildings**. Actual and potential **financing schemes** for the proposed concept of integrated energy services are analysed too. Finally, an evaluation of actual and potential **financial and technical barriers for NEON** is carried out.

The analysis shows that Europe is strongly committed in reshaping its policies to reach climate goals, working hard on several fronts to foster energy transition and support the primary role of end consumers. For sure, actions are needed for the development of energy communities and collective self-consumption within the electricity system, as well as to exploit the "unexpressed potential" of new resources for energy dispatching enhancing DR mechanisms. But several Administrative and investment barriers have to be tackled.

Starting from the Clean Energy Package for all Europeans:

- The **ED (Directive 2019/944)** aims to qualify consumers as “active” and introduces the concept of “Citizen Energy Community (CEC)”. All consumers should benefit from direct participation in the market, shaping their consumption based on market signals experiencing lower electricity prices or monetary or non-monetary incentives.
- **RED II (Directive 2018/2001)** as well stresses the role of consumers that are allowed to become consumers of renewable energy such as producing, storing and selling the surplus produced. The directive introduces the concept of Renewable Energy Community (REC) which can produce, consume, store and sell renewable energy. Moreover, it introduced provisions on the organisation and maximum duration of the permit-granting process, regarding **construction, repower and operation of RES and their connection to the grid**. It also required the Member States to establish a single contact point to guide applicants

through the entire administrative process. The EU Commission is monitoring closely the transposition RED II and is assessing whether further measures are needed.

- Transversely, the access to smart meters, smart billing and informed consumption is supported in the new **EED (Directive 2018/2002)**. **EPBD (Directive 2018/844)** contains provisions concerning the energy performance of buildings, a topic that is interlinked with the aforementioned ones.

The **full transposition of these directives** into national regulatory frameworks will set the rule to a **full development of the market, allowing the involved actors to express their potential and innovative drive**.

Generally speaking, to achieve EU climate objectives, a **suitable framework to facilitate the massive investments involved is required**. The transition to a decarbonised energy system, and particularly the development and integration of renewable energy, is hampered by overly **complex and lengthy administrative permitting procedures**. It is worth also noting complex structures, a lack of legal consistency and insufficient policy and regulatory frameworks and guidelines, that the commission is facing in the directives proposals presented in relation to the Clean Energy Package.

It is **crucial that the Member States establish an enabling framework to tackle the remaining non-financial barriers to renewable energy projects**, starting from the insufficient digital and human resources of authorities to process a growing number of permitting applications. For this reason, the EU Commission will issue a guidance in 2022, addressed to the Member States, on streamlining permitting and administrative procedures for renewable energy deployment. The document will be based on existing obstacles and best practices in the Member States.

In the end, the **powerful policy actions enacted at EU level** between the end of 2020 and the first part of 2021 to favour a sustainable economic recovery (e.g., EU Green Deal, Next Generation EU and the "Fit for 55" Package) **gave new impetus to the optimism of involved actors** regarding the evolution of the European energy system in a perspective of decarbonisation.

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